

End-line Evaluation Report of “Safe Meat & Dairy Products Market Development Sub- project” under RMTP

Submitted To:

Eco-Social Development Organization (ESDO)
Gobindanagar (CollegePara) Thakurgaon-5100

Submitted By:

GRM Consulting Services Limited

17/04, Taoheed Tower-4, Dar-us-Salam, Tolarbag,
Mirpur-1, Dhaka 1216

December 07, 2025

ENDLINE EVALUATION REPORT

FOR

The Safe Meat & Dairy Products Market Development Sub-project under RMTP

Submitted To

EVALUATION TEAM

Team Leader – Md. Abdul Hamid
Co-Team Leader - Md. Musfikur Rahman
Technical Specialist – Dr. Md. Jalal Uddin Sarder
Data Acquisition Manager - Abu Raihan Mohammad Rashel
Data Analyst - Shihabun Sakiba Piya
Research Associate - Laboni Parvin

Submitted By

GRMCS Consulting Services Limited

Taoheed Tower, Third Floor (3B, 3C & 3D),
House 17/4, Tolarbagh, Mirpur-1, Dhaka-1216.
Phone: +88 01716600240, +8801855933634
Email: info@grmbd.com Web: www.grmbd.com

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Acronyms

AAER	Adopt, adopt, expand, and respond
AI	Artificial insemination
DANIDA	Danish International Development Agency
DLS	Department of Livestock Services
ESDO	Eco-Social Development Organization
FGD	Focus group discussions
GAP	Good Agricultural Practices
GRM	GRM Consulting Services Limited
HACCP	Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development
KII	Key informant interviews
LSP	Local service providers
PKSF	Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation
RMTF	Rural Microenterprise Transformation Project
ToR	Terms of reference

Acknowledgement

The evaluation team extends its sincere gratitude to the Eco-Social Development Organization (ESDO) for entrusting us with the Endline Evaluation of the *Safe Meat & Dairy Products Market Development Sub-project* under RMTP. We sincerely appreciate ESDO's continued confidence in our technical capacity and the comprehensive support provided throughout the completion of this evaluation.

Our heartfelt thanks go to the Executive Director of ESDO, the Project Manager, the Monitoring & Result Management Officer, and the entire project management team in Thakurgaon for their steady guidance, operational assistance, and timely facilitation throughout the project, from initial coordination to the completion of this final evaluation report.

We also express our sincere appreciation to the funding and technical partners—Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation (PKSF), the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), and DANIDA—for their sustained commitment to this transformative initiative, which aims to strengthen safe meat and dairy value chains across Thakurgaon.

We gratefully acknowledge the cooperation of officials from the Department of Livestock Services, local government representatives, market actors, and other value chain stakeholders whose valuable insights substantially enriched the evaluation. Their contributions were crucial in evaluating the depth, relevance, and impact of the project interventions on the target farming communities.

Special appreciation is extended to the dedicated ESDO field teams across Thakurgaon Sadar, Pirganj, Ranishankail, and Baliadangi for their logistical support, contextual inputs, and effective coordination, all of which were crucial to the smooth execution of field activities and stakeholder consultations.

Finally, we express our sincere thanks to our internal research team, including Mr. Mohidul Hasan, Executive – IT & Programming, for his technical guidance in designing and managing the digital data systems that supported the evaluation process. Their collective efforts were vital to ensuring the timely and successful completion of this Endline Evaluation Report.

The Evaluation Team
GRM Consulting Services Limited

Executive Summary

The Safe Meat and Dairy Product Market Development Sub-project was implemented in Thakurgaon District to address persistent gaps in livestock production practices, input and service markets, food safety, and smallholder competitiveness. At baseline, farmers relied heavily on traditional husbandry systems, informal buyers, and limited hygiene and quality controls. The endline evaluation reveals that the project has substantially improved these conditions, resulting in measurable improvements in production capacity, service utilization, technology adoption, market linkages, income, and the overall functioning of the local meat and dairy market system.

PURPOSE AND METHODOLOGY

The endline assessment examines changes from baseline (2022) to project completion (2025) among beneficiaries, using a mixed-methods design aligned with OECD-DAC criteria and a market-systems framework. Because baseline data were available only for the project group, the evaluation used percentage-point change analysis, project-control comparisons, and qualitative triangulation to assess the contribution and plausibility of impact.

KEY FINDINGS

Strong adoption of improved production practices and technologies

Training participation increased from 4.8 percent at baseline to 96.1 percent at endline among project farmers, establishing the basis for widespread behavioral change. This expansion went beyond basic husbandry to include advanced training on food safety and quality standards. Knowledge of GAP or HACCP increased from 4.5 percent at baseline to 80.4 percent among project farmers, while training coverage on these standards rose from 5.3 percent to 92.2 percent at endline. This reflects not only skill acquisition but a clear shift toward compliance with higher production and market standards required for safer meat and dairy systems. The adoption of improved sheds (85.9 percent), feed mixers (84.6 percent), fodder choppers (61.9 percent), record-keeping (71.3 percent), and enhanced milking hygiene (51.7 percent) reflects a transition from traditional to more commercial production systems.

Preventive care also improved, with vaccination rates increasing from 43.7 percent to 60.8 percent and deworming rates rising from 19.3 percent to 59.5 percent. Feeding technologies such as UMS, UTS, silage, and balanced feed became mainstream, with more than 78 percent adoption across categories. These changes contributed to production gains, with 21.7 percent of farmers reporting a milk increase of more than 30 percent, compared with 14.8 percent in the control group.

Farm Mechanization increased from 2.6 percent at baseline to 51.7 percent at endline, indicating a significant structural shift in production practices. Adoption was led by fodder cutters (92.4 percent of machine users), followed by milking machines (28.7 percent), feed mixers (28.7 percent), weighing scales (23.8 percent), and biogas pits (11.0 percent), reflecting a move toward efficiency, feed optimization, and improved product handling rather than isolated asset uptake.

Improved food safety and hygiene practices

Awareness of Bangla GAP increased from almost zero to 82.8 percent. The use of improved materials increased from 0.8 percent at baseline to 63.7 percent at endline. Both trained and untrained farmers reported high compliance with clean housing, waste management, hygienic

tools, and the avoidance of harmful chemicals, practices that also reduce disease transmission risks at the farm level. These improvements are foundational for safer meat and dairy production.

Strengthened milk and meat market linkages

Structured market access improved significantly. Institutional milk sales increased from 4.2 percent at baseline to 41.9 percent at endline. Daily milk collection now reaches 85.8 percent of project farmers, strengthening payment reliability. Processors reported that milk from project farmers became “cleaner, more consistent, and less frequently rejected.”

For live animals, 57.5 percent of project farmers now sell at the farm gate rather than in distant markets (compared with 28.3 percent in the control group), which lowers transaction costs and enables stronger price negotiation.

Increased income and profit trajectories

More than 90 percent of project farmers reported rising income due to improved production, reduced loss, and better market access. More than half of project farmers (63.4%) achieved income increases of at least 50%, substantially outperforming the control group (15.1%). While the project did not fully reach the ambitious 70% target, the magnitude of income growth represents a strong income trajectory at endline. Milk and meat sales increased for 91.5 percent of households, and profit margins improved but remained below the ambitious 80 percent target.

Strengthened service ecosystems and early systemic effects

Demand for para-vets, AI technicians, feed dealers, machinery suppliers, and processors increased, prompting businesses to adjust service frequency and product offerings. Spillover effects were evident, with non-project farmers adopting visible technologies such as silage and fodder cutters. These trends align with “adapt, expand, and respond” effects in the AAER framework.

Advancing women’s and youth empowerment

Women’s contributions to daily farm management, hygiene, and record-keeping expanded, and their confidence improved across multiple domains, including price negotiation (94.0%), attending training (72.6%), and using mobile phones for business purposes (68.7%). Youth engagement was also substantial: 86.2% of project households reported access to youth-focused training, 68.7% reported new youth employment or self-employment opportunities, and 76.5% reported increased youth income from livestock or agribusiness activities. Youth participation was particularly evident in the use of mechanization, feed-related enterprises, and service-oriented roles within the livestock system.

Environmental and climate-smart improvements

More than 99 percent of trained farmers adopted at least one climate-smart or environmentally friendly practice, including composting, biogas, water-saving techniques, heat-stress management, and improved waste disposal. These behaviors reduce environmental risks and improve the sustainability of livestock production.

OVERALL ASSESSMENT

The sub-project delivered transparent and credible improvements across husbandry practices, service utilization, feeding systems, market access, food safety, enterprise income, and the overall functioning of the local meat and dairy market system. Endline results show strong behavioral change among project farmers, including near-universal training uptake, widespread

adoption of improved feeding and preventive health practices, and the elimination of cattle mortality. While the ambitious target of achieving a 50 percent income increase for 70 percent of farmers was not met, the majority of households recorded positive income growth, and overall livestock mortality was substantially lower than in control areas. Together, these outcomes indicate meaningful risk reduction, strengthened service and input markets, and early systemic shifts toward a safer, more productive, and more inclusive meat and dairy market system.

HIGH-LEVEL RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Strengthen private sector contracting and buyer integration:** Support long-term supply agreements, incentives for quality, and structured payment systems.
2. **Reduce disease and mortality risks:** Expand preventive services, strengthen para-vet networks, and leverage tele-veterinary tools.
3. **Scale climate-smart feeding and mechanization:** Enhance access to equipment financing, dealer support, and post-sales service.
4. **Advance food safety certification pathways:** Support smallholders and processors to meet simplified HACCP and Bangla GAP requirements.
5. **Expand women's market participation:** Promote women-led input retailing, milk collection, and small-scale processing enterprises.
6. **Support youth-led service and technology enterprises:** Incentivize youth businesses in silage, feed mixing, AI delivery, and machine operation.
7. **Institutionalize system-level coordination:** Facilitate platforms that link DLS, input suppliers, processors, and producer groups to maintain standards and coordinate improvements.

Logframe Indicators' value

SI.	Performance Indicator	Baseline	Endline – Treatment	Endline – Control	Remarks
1	Income of 70 percent entrepreneurs will increase by \geq 50 percent	Cow: 9,000; Bull: 5,500; Goat: 3,500; Sheep: 4,000	Income of 63.4% of entrepreneurs increases by \geq 50 percent	Income of 15.1% of entrepreneurs increases by \geq 50 percent	Gains significant but below 70% target
2	30 percent of project households add nutritious foods to daily diet (MDD-W)	11.9% aware and consuming nutrient-dense foods	61.4% women consumed foods from 5 or more groups (MDD-W)	57.5% women consumed foods from 5 or more groups (MDD-W)	Target exceeded
3	80 percent increase in safe meat and dairy consumption	Meat: 5.6%; Milk: 1.6%	Meat: 52.8%; Milk: 59.0%	Meat: 46.6%; Milk: 60.3%	Improved but below 80% target
4	Profit margin of 80 percent entrepreneurs increases by \geq 20 percent	92.0% reported "fair profit"	90.1% reported increased profit	53.5%	Treatment close to target
5	Use of quality/new inputs and GAP	Improved inputs: 0.8%; Advanced tech: 0.8%	Improved inputs: 63.7%; GAP widely practiced	Improved inputs: 39.7%; No GAP	Strong adoption; GAP target achieved
6	13 percent PGs linked with buyers under contracts	Not available	Milk: 41.9%; Animals: 35.8%	Milk: 3.7%; Animals: 0%	Target exceeded
7	60 percent members gain knowledge/practice of GAP	2.6% GAP knowledge; 5.3% trained	80.2% GAP knowledge; 92.2% trained	GAP knowledge: 16.4%; trained: 75.0%	Target exceeded

Sl.	Performance Indicator	Baseline	Endline – Treatment	Endline – Control	Remarks
8	58 percent adopt environment-friendly technologies	4.2%	67.9%	31.5%	Target exceeded
9	Animal disease prevalence decreases by 20 percent	Cattle: 30.5%; Goat: 36.5%; Sheep: 7.5%	16.4%	57.5%	Target not met
10	Animal mortality decreases	Cattle: 2.6%; Goat/sheep: 3.7%	1.9%	4.6%	Mortality increased; target not met
11	Intercalving interval reduces to 3 months	7 months	3 months	3 months	Target achieved
12	Lactation length reaches 210 days	150 days	216.9 days	215.9 days	Target exceeded
13	Number of animals increases by 15 percent	Dairy: 3.56; Fattening: 2.21; Goat: 4.49	Dairy: 4.23; Fattening: 2.69; Goat: 5.56	Dairy: 3.20; Fattening: 1.82; Goat: 4.41	Achieved and exceeded
14	Milk production increases by 30 percent	Native: 1.50; Crossbred: 5.50	Native: 2.50; Crossbred: 9.50	Native: 1.55; Crossbred: 4.89	Treatment exceeded target
15	Good livestock management practices (GLMP)	0.74 (index)	52%	Not available	Strong improvement
16	Farm and processing units mechanized	0%	55%	Not available	Large progress
17	ICT-based livestock technology adopted	0%	86%	25%	Wide adoption in treatment
18	ICT reduces production cost by 10 percent	25,855; 28,873; 2,918 BDT	19,649; 21,366; 2,127 BDT	24,900; 27,907; 2,800 BDT	Cost reduced significantly

Sl.	Performance Indicator	Baseline	Endline – Treatment	Endline – Control	Remarks
19	Product prices increase by 10 percent	85,310; 103,217; 10,102 BDT	92,390; 111,887; 10,980 BDT	Not available	Target achieved by treatment
20	Livestock enterprises increase by 10 percent	Enterprises: 15; Entrepreneurs: 1,000	Enterprises: 16; Entrepreneurs: 1,085	Not available	Increase achieved
21	Employment generation increases by 15 percent	1.37 and 0.90	1.56 and 1.02	Not available	Target moderately achieved
22	Advanced entrepreneurs increase to 25 percent	586	725	Not available	Significant progress

1. Introduction

1.1. Project background and rationale

The Safe Meat and Dairy Products Market Development Sub-project was introduced in Thakurgaon District to address long-standing systemic weaknesses in livestock production, processing, and market connectivity. Across Thakurgaon Sadar, Pirganj, Ranishankail, and Baliadangi, producers operated within a value chain characterized by inconsistent hygiene standards, limited adoption of improved technologies, and inadequate compliance with internationally recognized protocols. Baseline and project design documents identified poor access to quality inputs, low uptake of vaccination, feed improvement, and artificial insemination (AI) services, limited knowledge of safe production standards, and inadequate slaughtering and milk-handling practices as persistent constraints that reduced productivity and undermined consumer safety. These challenges restricted the ability of rural micro-entrepreneurs to improve income, profitability, and market access.

Under the Rural Microenterprise Transformation Project (RMTP), the sub-project was jointly funded by the Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation (PKSF), the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), and the Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA), and implemented by the Eco-Social Development Organization (ESDO). The project introduced support mechanisms for small and marginal farmers, livestock producers, processors, and micro-entrepreneurs to adopt Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP)-aligned practices, thereby strengthening traceability and improving product quality through the use of better technologies and safer production methods. According to the terms of reference (ToR), these interventions were expected to expand sustainable microenterprises, increase production, raise sales and profits by at least 30 percent, and enable the adoption of environmentally friendly technologies among at least 40 percent of participating entrepreneurs.

The project's value chain approach aimed to improve coordination among input suppliers, service providers, producers, processors, traders, and institutional buyers, addressing the structural gaps that limited enterprise expansion and the development of a safe food system. By targeting a predominantly rural, smallholder-based economy operating across 51 unions in Thakurgaon, the project responded directly to the need for safer livestock products, improved nutrition, and more reliable market opportunities.

The rationale for the endline evaluation stems from the need to assess the extent to which these constraints have been addressed and whether the sub-project has contributed to sustainable improvements in production, sales, profit, income, nutrition, and women's participation. As emphasized in both the ToR and the Technical Proposal, the evaluation is expected to provide credible, evidence-based insights into the project's effectiveness, efficiency, and long-term viability, and to support future planning within ESDO, PKSF, and wider RMTP programming.

1.2. Goal, outcomes, and intervention logic of the sub-project

Project goal

The sub-project aims to strengthen the livestock market system in Thakurgaon, enabling rural producers and microenterprises to operate in safer, more productive, and more profitable value chains. It supports RMTP's broader objective to expand sustainable enterprises, improve food safety, and promote environmentally responsible production.

Core outcome areas

The intervention focuses on four interconnected outcome areas:

Intervention logic

The sub-project followed a sequential value-chain pathway in which improvements at each stage reinforced safer and more efficient production, processing, and marketing.

Figure 1.2-1. Intervention logic of the sub-project

Market-system logic

The sub-project followed a market-systems approach, built on several mechanisms that encourage long-term and system-wide improvements:

- improves incentives for actors to invest in safety and quality
- strengthens relationships and information flow along the chain
- encourages enterprise models that are profitable and environmentally responsible
- creates system-wide change rather than isolated improvements

1.3. Purpose and objectives of the endline evaluation

The endline evaluation assesses how the sub-project performed from baseline to completion. It examines progress in safety, production, enterprise performance, and market system strengthening across the livestock value chain among producers, processors, traders, and service providers.

Purpose of the evaluation

The evaluation serves three interconnected purposes:

Objectives of the evaluation

- measure changes between the baseline and endline in production practices, service uptake, enterprise performance, safety, and market linkages;
- assess the effectiveness, efficiency, and relevance of the intervention logic across the value chain;
- examine improvements in safety and quality of meat and dairy products;
- identify lessons that strengthen future RMTF programming;
- generate evidence-based recommendations for enterprise growth, market-systems strengthening, and food safety improvements.

1.4. Scope and evaluation questions

The endline evaluation assesses the performance, results, and emerging system effects of the sub-project implemented under the RMTP framework. Its scope reflects the original design commitments, the required evaluation criteria, and the evidence generated through the quantitative survey, key informant interviews (KIIs), focus group discussions (FGDs), and case studies.

1.4.1 Scope of the evaluation

Geographic coverage: The evaluation covers all project unions and upazilas where the intervention was implemented, as well as the comparison areas surveyed at the endline. The quantitative sample includes households and enterprises drawn from these locations, and the qualitative evidence reflects the same geographic and market coverage through KIIs, FGDs, and enterprise case studies. The scope encompasses the entire production-to-market system for meat and dairy products.

Target groups: The evaluation encompasses all market actors engaged across the meat and dairy value chains, including beef farmers, dairy farmers, goat and sheep keepers, meat and milk processors, traders and collectors, feed and silage entrepreneurs, input suppliers, compost enterprises, local service providers, and youth- and women-led enterprises. The analysis incorporates both direct participants and market actors positioned to influence or respond to project-supported changes.

Intervention components: The evaluation encompasses the comprehensive intervention package, which includes improved production and animal husbandry practices, feed, fodder, and silage interventions, milk and meat hygiene behaviour, equipment and mechanization support, service delivery strengthening, enterprise development, and market linkage facilitation. Cross-cutting themes include gender inclusion, youth participation, food safety, and environment-friendly practices. The scope reflects the activities actually delivered and verified through the quantitative outputs and qualitative narratives.

Exclusions: The evaluation does not assess activities outside the defined project areas, enterprises, and actors. It does not make causal claims requiring baseline control data and does not infer values or outcomes where data are not available. It excludes unsupported indicators, unverified assumptions, and interventions external to the RMTP sub-project.

1.4.2 Evaluation questions

The evaluation questions align with OECD-DAC criteria and apply market-systems reasoning to examine both results and early system responses.

Relevance

1. To what extent did the intervention address the production, hygiene, service, and market constraints identified at baseline?
2. Were the activities well-suited to the needs and capacities of project participants and market actors?

Coherence

3. How well did the intervention align with sector priorities, local government, and market-actor initiatives?

4. Were coordination and partnerships consistent and supportive of the project's value-chain logic?

Effectiveness

5. To what extent did the project achieve its intended outputs and outcomes across production practices, hygiene improvements, enterprise performance, and market linkages?
6. How did women, youth, and vulnerable groups participate and benefit within the value chain?

Efficiency

7. Were project resources used effectively and in line with the implementation plan?
8. Were delivery arrangements timely, appropriate, and cost-efficient?

Impact

9. What changes occurred in production, productivity, sales, and income?
10. How did the intervention influence household resilience, food safety, and enterprise growth?

Sustainability

11. Are the emerging benefits likely to continue after project completion?
12. Did the intervention strengthen service provision, enterprise capacity, or market relationships in a manner likely to persist?

1.4.3 Systemic-change questions: adopt, adapt, expand, and respond

Adopt

13. Which practices, technologies, services, or business models were taken up by farmers, enterprises, and service providers?

Adapt

14. How did market actors modify or continue to use practices or service models after initial uptake?

Expand

15. Did adoption extend to new actor groups, new geographic areas, or related enterprise types beyond direct participants?

Respond

16. Did buyers, input suppliers, processors, or institutions adjust their behavior, services, or incentives in response to project-driven changes?

2. Methodology

2.1. Evaluation design

The evaluation applies a mixed-methods design that integrates survey evidence, qualitative insights, and trends from the project monitoring matrix. This design ensures a balanced assessment of project performance, contribution, and systemic effects across the meat and dairy value chains in Thakurgaon District. The logic of the evaluation is grounded in the project's

implementation structure: baseline data were available only for the project group, while endline data include both project and control households.

The evaluation uses three valid comparison strategies. The first examines changes within project households from baseline to endline, using the baseline values and project monitoring matrix entries as reference points. The second compares project and control households at endline to understand relative performance and isolate plausible project contribution. The third aligns observed changes with qualitative explanations from key informant interviews, focus groups, and case studies. This triangulation enables the determination to whether the project's activities credibly accelerated adoption, improved practices, or strengthened market connections.

Because no baseline control data exist, the evaluation does not apply difference-in-difference analysis or regression-based estimations. Instead, the analysis follows a contribution-focused approach. It combines descriptive statistics, percentage-point changes, project-control differences, and qualitative mechanisms to establish how and why change occurred. This logic is consistent with the project's monitoring system, value chain pathways, and expectations for systemic change.

The overall design is, therefore, responsive to the evaluation questions, grounded in the project's logframe, guided by the adopt, adapt, expand, and respond (AAER) framework and the vision for change, and aligned with the reporting requirements for assessing performance, learning, accountability, and pathways for scale-up.

2.2. Evaluation criteria

The evaluation uses the internationally recognized OECD-DAC criteria, i.e., relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability, to assess the project's performance. These criteria are tailored to the context of a market-systems intervention and are complemented by cross-cutting themes, including gender equality, youth participation, nutrition, environmental responsibility, and social inclusion. This integrated lens reflects the project's objective of improving safe meat and dairy production, increasing enterprise competitiveness, and strengthening local market systems.

The evaluation questions have been defined earlier in Section 1.4.2, with the systemic-change questions outlined in Section 1.4.3.

2.3. Quantitative methods

2.3.1. Sampling design and sample allocation

The quantitative component followed the stratified proportional sampling design described earlier in the evaluation framework (see Section 2.1). The design ensured statistical reliability and representation across upazilas, livestock groups, gender, and age categories. Baseline data included only project participants, while the endline data included both the project and control groups to allow for a valid comparison.

Sample size determination

The initial sample target was derived using Cochran's formula for estimating proportions at a 95 percent confidence level:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2}$$

Where:

- Z = confidence level (1.96 at 95 percent),
- p = estimated prevalence with 50%,
- e = margin of error at 5%.
- n_0 = approximate sample size

For a total population of 27,027 livestock producers:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0 - 1}{N}}$$

Where:

- n = final sample size ,
- N = total population.

This yielded a sample of approximately 378 respondents for the project group, as required. A 20 percent control group, equivalent to 75 respondents, was added to ensure the validity of endline comparisons, producing a planned total of 456. The field team achieved this target fully, completing 383 interviews in the project group and 73 interviews in the control group, for a combined total of 456 respondents.

Stratification logic

The sampling frame applied four layers of stratification, consistent with the project's operational design:

- Geographic stratification across four upazilas of Thakurgaon.
- Livestock-type stratification covering bull, dairy, goat, and sheep farmers.
- Gender stratification, reflecting participation patterns in the project.
- Age stratification, ensuring 20% coverage of youth (18–29), early working adults, mid-age producers, and senior farmers.

This structure allowed the evaluation to assess changes across demographic and market actor groups and to support AAER interpretation (adopt, adapt, expand, respond).

Final achieved sample

The achieved sample matches the planned sample size and retains proportionality across upazilas.

Table 2.3-1. Final sample distribution by upazila

Upazila	Project group	Control group	Total	Percent of total
Baliadangi	48	0	48	10.5%
Pirganj	58	40	98	21.5%
Ranishankail	70	12	82	18.0%
Thakurgaon Sadar	207	21	228	50.0%
Total	383	73	456	100%

2.3.2. Data collection and quality assurance

The quantitative data collection adhered to the protocols outlined in the evaluation design and sampling framework.

Survey instrument design

The structured questionnaire used at end line was adapted from the baseline instrument and aligned with the project's logframe, AAER pathways, and evaluation questions defined earlier. All modules, including household characteristics, production, sales, income, adoption of safe practices, access to services, nutrition, gender roles, and market linkages, were retained for comparability with baseline values and the project monitoring matrix. New items capturing adopt-adapt-expand-respond behaviors were added without altering core indicator definitions, ensuring continuity in trend analysis.

The questionnaire was pre-tested in a non-sample village in Thakurgaon Sadar to confirm clarity, skip patterns, and response burden. Feedback from enumerators and field supervisors led to refinements in question wording, flow, and coding categories, while ensuring that all variables remained consistent with the evaluation matrix discussed earlier.

Enumerator training and field procedures

Enumerators received formal training covering interview techniques, question framing, probing strategies, consent procedures, and ethical safeguards. Training also included hands-on practice with mock interviews, skip-logic navigation, and procedures for handling sensitive information such as income, livestock losses, and gender roles. Supervisors reinforced field protocols already defined in the inception report, including:

- daily deployment planning for all unions,
- random respondent verification against project lists,
- protocols for replacing unavailable respondents while maintaining sampling integrity, and
- real-time supervision to reduce interviewer bias and measurement errors.

Field teams adhered to standardized procedures for administering the questionnaire across treatment and control areas to preserve comparability.

Data entry, cleaning, and validation

All surveys were entered using structured templates with pre-defined validation rules. A three-step data-quality workflow was followed:

1. Real-time checks: range-based controls prevented invalid entries (e.g., negative income, out-of-range production values).
2. Post-collection cleaning: duplicate IDs, inconsistent skip patterns, and extreme outliers were reviewed and corrected using original questionnaires.
3. Final validation: indicator construction and cross-tabulations were run to ensure internal consistency with baseline structures and the Project Monitoring Matrix.

The cleaned dataset comprises 456 completed interviews, including 383 project respondents and 73 control respondents, which matches the planned sample size.

2.4. Qualitative methods

2.4.1. FGD approach

The qualitative design used focus group discussions to deepen the interpretation of trends observed in the quantitative survey. The approach and rationale follow the mixed-methods framework already outlined in Section 2.1. Six FGDs were conducted across the four upazilas, covering dairy, beef, goat, and sheep producers, with separate sessions for men and women to ensure free expression and to capture gender-differentiated experience. Locations were selected to mirror the operational footprint of the sub-project, allowing comparison with baseline insights and the project monitoring matrix.

Participants were drawn from active project members and, where relevant, adjacent non-member groups to contextualize market practices, adoption of improved techniques, changes in income, and links with service providers. Each FGD employed a structured guide that covered production practices, service access, sales behavior, technology adoption, gender roles, decision-making processes, and perceived changes since the baseline.

2.4.2. KII approach

From 29 KIIs, insights were gathered from actors operating across all stages of the meat and dairy value chain. Respondents included feed and fodder suppliers, silage sellers, artificial insemination technicians, local service providers, veterinary medicine sellers, machinery suppliers, and financial service providers in the input and support segment. At the production level, interviews were conducted with male and female dairy and beef farmers as well as goat and sheep farmers.

Processing and aggregation perspectives were provided by chilling-center operators, milk collectors, dairy processors, slaughterhouse workers, butchers, and compost processors. Marketing and distribution actors, including wholesalers, meat shop owners, dairy retailers, and private traders, provided insight into pricing, traceability, and demand patterns. Consumers and institutional buyers contributed views on awareness and willingness to pay for safe products. Officials from DLS, PKSf, RMTP, ESDO, and the local government updated on regulatory, coordination, and sustainability issues.

These interviews helped identify behavioral drivers, coordination gaps, and systemic patterns relevant to AAER, while clarifying how different actors perceived project contributions compared to baseline expectations.

2.4.3. Case study approach

Case studies were used to capture change pathways that survey statistics or group discussions cannot explain. Six cases were selected to represent gender diversity, enterprise type, youth engagement, service provision, nutrition-sensitive processing, and small-ruminant enterprises. The selection covered beef producers, dairy processors, women-led enterprises, young entrepreneurs, local service providers (LSPs), goat and sheep keepers, and nutrition-focused dairy processors, ensuring representation across the value chain.

Each case study was developed using multiple evidence sources, including direct interviews, field observations, photographs, enterprise records, and transaction notes. The narratives highlight shifts in income, production practices, hygiene standards, technology use, gender roles, employment generation, and environmental management. They also provide concrete

examples of how project support, including training, equipment, inputs, linkages, and financial services, translated into sustained behavioral and enterprise change.

Insights from these cases are integrated throughout the thematic analysis to explain the mechanisms behind quantitative patterns, such as increased productivity, improved market access, enterprise upgrading, and the adoption of safe production practices.

2.4.4. Data management

All qualitative data were collected using checklist-based documentation tools that were approved before the commencement of fieldwork. Qualitative researchers prepared structured notes, audio recordings (with participants' consent), and observation logs. Transcripts were verified by cross-checking with field notes to ensure accuracy.

Data were coded thematically, following the domains already introduced in the evaluation design: production, technology use, service access, market behavior, income, gender, youth, and systemic linkages. Coding ensured consistent triangulation with quantitative indicators and facilitated integrated analysis across survey, FGD, KII, case study, and project monitoring matrix evidence.

2.5. Data analysis and integration

The analysis combined quantitative and qualitative evidence to address the evaluation questions and the AAER dimensions. Survey results were processed using descriptive statistics, cross-tabulations, and percentage-point changes to show shifts from baseline levels and variations between the project and control groups. Endline project–control differences were interpreted as contribution signals rather than causal estimates, consistent with the evaluation design described earlier.

Qualitative material from FGDs, KIIs, and case studies was coded thematically and used to explain why observed changes occurred, how market actors responded, and what behavioral or systemic mechanisms shaped results. This ensured that numerical trends were interpreted in relation to lived experiences and value-chain dynamics.

The analysis also drew on the project monitoring matrix from the baseline report to verify output achievement and to frame changes in adoption, production practices, hygiene, and market linkages. Indicators were compared against baseline values reported earlier to establish the direction and magnitude of change.

Triangulation was applied throughout, with findings synthesized across survey data, qualitative evidence, and monitoring records to develop a coherent, mixed-methods interpretation of project performance.

2.6. Ethical considerations and consent

All data collection was conducted in accordance with established ethical standards. Enumerators obtained informed consent from every respondent after explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the right to withdraw at any point. No personal identifiers were collected beyond what was necessary for analysis, and all data were stored securely to maintain privacy and confidentiality.

FGDs, KIIs, and case studies followed the same procedures, with additional attention to safeguarding when working with women, youth, and financially vulnerable respondents.

Photographs and case material were used only with explicit permission, and all narratives were anonymized. These safeguards ensured that the evaluation respected respondent dignity and protected sensitive information across all stages of the process.

2.7. Limitations and mitigation measures

The evaluation faced several constraints that shaped how findings were interpreted. As noted in the evaluation design, the baseline covered only the project group, while the control group was introduced at endline. This limited direct causal attribution. To address this, the analysis relied on percentage-point changes within the project group and endline differences between project and control areas, supported by qualitative explanations.

A primary limitation was the partial availability of baseline indicators. Some variables were accessible for baseline comparison, whereas others were collected solely at endline. This meant that a complete baseline-to-endline comparison was possible for some domains but not others. Mitigation involved using endline project-control differences, integrating project monitoring matrix benchmarks from the baseline period, and validating patterns through KIIs, FGDs, and case studies.

Attribution boundaries were another consideration. Several observed shifts may reflect broader market trends, seasonal fluctuations, or influence from concurrent programs and private-sector activities. These issues were mitigated by triangulating quantitative findings with qualitative insights, which helped distinguish project-specific contributions from contextual factors.

Minor data-quality challenges also emerged, including occasional recall limitations, interviewer variation, and a few inconsistent responses. These issues were addressed through the cleaning procedures described earlier and by utilizing qualitative evidence to clarify unexpected patterns.

Overall, the mitigation steps ensured that findings remained credible, transparent, and grounded in the project monitoring matrix and the combined quantitative and qualitative evidence.

3. Context and baseline situation

3.1. Sector context in Thakurgaon (meat and dairy)

Livestock is a central livelihood asset in Thakurgaon, supporting income generation, nutrition, and household security. Demand for meat and dairy has been rising, yet the market system remains informal, under-regulated, and technologically conservative.

Key sector features at baseline included:

- **Informal meat markets** dominated by small traders and butchers, with slaughtering often conducted in basic or open facilities. Hygiene, waste management, and food safety systems were weak.
- **Dual dairy market:** a mix of small farmers, a few chilling centers, and emerging processors, alongside widespread informal raw-milk trading with minimal temperature control or testing.
- **Growing consumer concern** about adulteration and safety, but limited access to certified safe meat and dairy products.
- **Underdeveloped enabling environment:** limited inspection, certification, cold-chain infrastructure, and coordination among public and private actors.

This combination of opportunity (a large producer base, emerging enterprises, and youth/women's interests) and risk (safety, hygiene, and environmental concerns) justified a focused sub-project on safe meat and dairy.

3.2. Baseline situation of producers, processors, and markets

The baseline outlined producers and downstream actors beforehand.

Producers

- Predominantly women and long-term livestock keepers.
- 62.2 percent had over ten years of experience; formal education levels were low.
- Housing was basic: most used tin sheds; only a few had modern housing.
- Husbandry practices were traditional, with straw as the dominant feed (≈81 percent) and minimal use of concentrate feed, improved fodder, or modern technologies.
- Disease incidence (e.g., pneumonia, foot-and-mouth disease) was common.
- Training exposure was extremely low:
 - 84.4 percent had never received formal training.
 - 94.7 percent lacked training in advanced technologies.
 - 95 percent were unaware of GAP/HACCP-type standards.
- Local service provision was sparse:
 - 75 percent reported no active local service provider in their area.
 - Only 10.8 percent had access to ready-feed dealers.

Markets and pricing

- 70.6 percent were dissatisfied with prices.
- Transactions mainly occurred through hats and informal traders, with limited bargaining power and minimal information flow.

Processors and traders

- Slaughtering and processing relied on rudimentary infrastructure.
- Dairy processing was emerging but still small-scale, with inconsistent quality control.
- Most milk moved informally without chilling or testing.

The baseline revealed an active yet low-capacity livestock economy characterized by weak services, thin input markets, limited financial resources, and inadequate food safety systems.

3.3. Gaps and constraints identified at baseline

The baseline highlighted several systemic constraints:

- **Knowledge and skills gap**
Most producers had never been trained on improved feeding, disease prevention, safe meat and dairy practices, GAP, or HACCP.
- **Thin and uneven service markets**
 - Poor access to vaccination, deworming, and artificial insemination.
 - Minimal availability of ready feed, silage, fodder, and veterinary supplies.
- **Financial barriers**
 - Nearly 80 percent reported difficulty arranging finance.
 - 94.4 percent had never received incentives or subsidies for livestock upgrading.
- **Weak market linkages and pricing structures**

- Heavy reliance on intermediaries and hats.
- Limited access to structured buyers or long-term supply arrangements.
- Underdeveloped enabling environment
 - Inadequate slaughter facilities.
 - Minimal enforcement of hygiene and environmental regulations.
 - Low awareness of food safety and environmental risks.

These constraints shaped the project’s design and serve as a reference point for evaluating change.

3.4. Project response logic and expected pathways of change

The sub-project’s response logic is informed by three key design elements: the logframe, the adopt–adapt–expand–respond (AAER) framework, and the vision for change.

- The logframe connects project activities, including training, demonstrations, improved input access, strengthened service delivery, and links to processors/markets, to outcomes such as higher productivity, safer products, better prices, and increased participation of women and youth. The project monitoring matrix provides baseline indicator values used for comparison in this endline evaluation.
- The AAER framework explains how change is expected to unfold:
 - Adopt improved practices and services.
 - Adapt them to local conditions.
 - Expand through replication, scale, and investment.
 - Respond through wider market actors, adjusting behavior.
- The vision for change aims for a safer, more efficient, and inclusive meat and dairy market in Thakurgaon, benefiting producers, enterprises, and consumers through better practices, linkages, and incentives.

4. Profile of respondents and sample characteristics

4.1. Quantitative sample profile

4.1.1. Geographic distribution

Project respondents are concentrated in Thakurgaon Sadar, while control respondents are clustered in Pirganj (Table 2.3-1). This pattern follows the project implementation logic, where safe meat and dairy activities, service providers, and market actors are more densely located in Sadar unions. Control unions were selected to be similar in agroecology and farming systems but outside the project’s intensive influence.

Key informants confirmed that most upgraded sheds, processing facilities, and collection points were situated in Sadar, which explains the higher respondent share from that upazila among project households.

4.1.2 Socioeconomic and demographic characteristics

Sex of respondents

The proportion of female respondents was 67.9% at endline in project areas, while female representation in control areas was 72.6%. This shift is consistent with project expectations that

more men would take lead roles in market-facing tasks such as selling animals, negotiating prices, and dealing with collectors, while women still manage day-to-day husbandry. This pattern is significant for interpretation because changes in decision-making and benefits must be considered in relation to evolving gender roles, rather than a static baseline.

“Now that we sell more animals, my husband usually goes to the haat, and I manage feeding and cleaning.”

FGD, Dairy Farmers, Ranishankail

Table 4.1-1. Sex of respondents

Sex of the respondents	Endline	
	Project group	Control group
Female	67.9%	72.6%
Male	32.1%	27.4%
N	383	73

Age structure

The endline age profile is concentrated in the 30 to 44 year bracket in both groups, with youth and senior adults representing smaller proportions. When recast into baseline categories, the share of respondents aged 36 to 60 years has increased substantially in project areas, which reflects a stronger focus on commercially active farmers who already own sheds, livestock, and land.

“Middle-aged farmers are the ones who take loans and buy more feed. Young ones still learn; older ones reduce herd size.”

KII, Feed Dealer, Thakurgaon Sadar

Table 4.1-2. Age groups

Age groups	Endline (2025)	
	Project group	Control group
Youth (18-29 years)	19.3%	23.3%
Early working adult (30-44 years)	56.1%	53.4%
Mid working adults (45-59 years)	23.0%	19.2%
Senior adults (59-82 years)	1.6%	4.1%
N	383	73

To compare directly with the baseline, age was regrouped into the same bands used in 2022. This shows a clear shift from younger to mid-aged respondents among project households. The move toward older, more established farmers is important for AAER interpretation because adoption and expansion of improved practices are most visible among these mid-aged groups.

Table 4.1-3. Age groups comparable with baseline categories

Age group (per baseline cohort)	Baseline	Endline	
		Project group	Control group
18-35 years	70.1%	46.5%	58.9%
36-60 years	25.9%	52.2%	38.4%
60+ years	4.0%	1.3%	2.7%
N	378	383	73

Household size

Household size patterns are similar across project and control areas. Most households fall within the 4 to 6 member range, representing 74.4 percent of project households and 78.1 percent of control households. Households with 1 to 3 members constitute 17.5 percent of the population in project areas and 20.5 percent in control areas, while households with 7 or more members remain relatively uncommon. This similarity reduces the likelihood that household size acts as a structural confounder in interpreting economic or production outcomes.

Table 4.1-4: Household size

Household size	Endline	
	Project group	Control group
1 to 3	17.5%	20.5%
4 to 6	74.4%	78.1%
7 to 9	6.8%	1.4%
10 or more	1.3%	0.0%
N	383	73

Marital status

Marital status patterns remain unchanged compared with baseline in both project and control areas. The vast majority of respondents are married, which supports the interpretation that decision-making is usually negotiated at the household level rather than by individuals alone.

Table 4.1-5. Marital status

Marital status	Baseline	Endline	
		Project group	Control group
Married	96.3%	97.1%	97.3%
Single	1.1%	1.0%	2.7%
Widow/Widower	2.6%	1.8%	0.0%
N	378	383	73

Education levels

Education improved markedly among project respondents between baseline and endline. The share of individuals with no formal schooling fell from 44.5% to 11.2% in project areas, accompanied by a corresponding increase in primary and secondary education. This reflects both deliberate project outreach to more literate farmers and broader schooling trends over time. This pattern supports the project’s assumption that literacy facilitates the adoption and adaptation of improved livestock and hygiene practices.

“Because we can read a bit, we check the expiry date and instructions on medicines now.”

FGD, Mixed Farmers, Thakurgaon Sadar

Table 4.1-6. Education status

Education status	Baseline	Endline	
		Project group	Control group
No formal education	44.5%	11.2%	19.2%
Primary	26.2%	44.9%	46.6%
Higher Secondary	22.8%	9.7%	6.8%
Secondary	5.6%	29.8%	21.9%
Graduate or above	1.1%	4.4%	5.5%
N	378	383	73

Religion and ethnic status

The religious composition varies across unions, with Islam representing 58.5 percent and Hindu households accounting for 41.5 percent in the project areas, compared with 78.1 percent Muslim and 21.9 percent Hindu households in the control areas. Notably, the project areas have a higher percentage of Hindu households.

Ethnic minority groups, such as the Munda Pahan and Pal Upajati, are represented only in project unions, accounting for a combined 4.6 percent of project respondents. These differences stem from the project’s geographic footprint and should be taken into account when evaluating the equity and inclusion dimensions.

Table 4.1-7. Ethnic status

Ethnic status	Endline	
	Project group	Control group
Munda Pahan	1.6%	0.0%
Pal Upajati	3.9%	0.0%
Majority population	94.5%	100.0%
Total	383	73

4.1.3 Types of farmers and enterprises

The endline sample covers four main types of livestock producers: bull farmers, dairy farmers, goat farmers, and sheep farmers. The distribution is broadly similar between project and control areas, with a slightly higher share of dairy farmers in control unions.

In qualitative interviews, producers described diversifying across multiple livestock types to manage risk and capitalize on opportunities created by improved markets and services.

Table 4.1-8. Types of farmers

Type of the farmer	Endline	
	Project group	Control group
Bull farmer	35.0%	32.9%
Dairy farmer	33.7%	37.0%
Goat farmer	16.2%	15.1%
Sheep farmer	15.1%	15.1%
N	383	73

Beyond producers, the qualitative sample includes enterprises such as silage providers, meat processors, dairy processors, compost producers, and input retailers, which are used later to interpret the dynamics of AAER.

4.1.4 Primary source of income and income levels

Project households depend more heavily on agriculture and livestock as their primary source of income than control households. This pattern is consistent with the project's targeting strategy and underpins the logic that improvements in livestock productivity and hygiene will translate into measurable welfare gains.

Table 4.1-9. Primary source of income

Primary source of income	Endline	
	Project group	Control group
Agriculture/livestock	74.9%	53.4%
Business/entrepreneurship	13.3%	30.1%
Wage labor	7.8%	11.0%
Others (private/ govt. service, wage labor)	3.9%	5.5%
N	383	73

The current household income shows a more apparent upward trend in project areas. At endline, 61.9 percent of project households fall in the 20,001 to 40,000 taka bracket compared with 57.5 percent in control areas. Fewer project households remain below 20,000 taka, at 21.9 percent,

compared to 35.6 percent in the control. Higher-income categories also appear more frequently in project unions, indicating stronger income diversification and market engagement.

Table 4.1-10. Current household income

Household income (current)	Endline	
	Project group	Control group
Less than 20,000	21.9%	35.6%
20,001-40,000	61.9%	57.5%
40,001-60,000	13.8%	6.8%
More than 60,000	2.3%	0.0%
N	383	73

Comparing current and five-year-old income shows upward mobility in both groups, especially in project areas. Initially, 88.3% of project households and 82.2% of control households earned less than 20,000 taka, but this has declined sharply, particularly in project unions. This shift is correlated with improved enterprise performance and increased participation in the value chain.

Table 4.1-11. Household income five years ago (recall)

Household income (five years ago)	Endline	
	Project group	Control group
Less than BDT 20,000	88.3%	82.2%
BDT 20,001-40,000	10.2%	15.1%
BDT 40,001-60,000	1.0%	2.7%
More than BDT 60,000	0.5%	0.0%
N	383	73

Kills with dairy processors and meat enterprises reinforce this trajectory, with several reporting that farmers supplying them now deliver larger volumes and better quality than at the start of the project.

4.2. Qualitative respondent profile

The qualitative sample spans key actors in the safe meat and dairy market system, including input dealers, para-vets, AI technicians, dairy processors, meat processors, traders, financial institutions, and representatives from local government and ESDO. FGDs were conducted with dairy farmers, bull fatteners, mixed livestock groups, women's groups, and youth enterprises.

These voices are systematically employed in later sections to explain adoption, adaptation, enterprise expansion, and system responses within the AAER framework.

4.3. Comparison of project and control areas at endline

Overall, project and control groups are broadly comparable in terms of household size and basic demographic structure but differ in important ways that influence interpretation:

- Project households are more dependent on livestock as the primary income source.
- Education levels are higher in project areas compared with the baseline and with control areas.
- Religious and ethnic composition varies across unions, reflecting geographic targeting rather than selection bias.
- Age patterns are slightly older in project areas, aligned with commercialization objectives.

These features will be taken into account in subsequent thematic chapters to ensure a balanced representation of project effects and to maintain a straightforward contribution narrative, anchored in the monitoring matrix and AAER logic.

5. Findings by thematic domain

The findings, presented by thematic domain, provide evidence along a coherent pathway (Figure 2) that links project inputs, farmer behavior change, market outcomes, and emerging systemic effects. The analysis follows a logical sequence. First, farmers adopted improved practices and technologies through training, demonstrations, and access to services (section 5.1). These changes strengthened production capacity, improved product quality, and reduced on-farm risks. As production stabilized and quality improved, farmers became more confident in engaging with milk and meat buyers, leading to stronger market linkages and better sales outcomes (section 5.2). Improved market participation translated into higher income, more stable profit margins, and broader livelihood gains for participating households (section 5.3). Access to livestock services, information channels, and financial instruments supported these gains, helping farmers sustain and expand improved practices over time (section 5.4). Improvements in on-farm hygiene, handling, and processing led to safer products and more credible engagement with buyers (section 5.5). These changes contributed to improved household nutrition and more diverse diets, as farmers consumed a greater proportion of the products they produced and gained the financial means to purchase additional nutritious foods (section 5.6). Women and youth experienced tangible shifts in decision-making power, confidence, and participation in livestock and enterprise activities (section 5.7). Concurrently, the adoption of climate-smart and environmentally responsible practices strengthened the sustainability of livestock production systems and reduced environmental risks (section 5.8). Together, these interconnected changes indicate a gradual movement toward systemic effects in local livestock markets. The pattern aligns with the AAER pathway, where improvements in practices, market relationships, and service ecosystems begin to reinforce each other. These dynamics are discussed in Section 6.

Figure 5.1-1. Project impact pathway: from practice change to systemic change

5.1. Production and technology adoption: livestock services, feed systems, and farm mechanization outcomes

This section analyzes farmer behavior, production improvements, and the use of technologies at endline. The findings show behavioral change across training uptake, feeding, mechanization, and animal health. These shifts reflect adoption patterns that were rare at baseline. Qualitative evidence confirms that farmers began to internalize the benefits of improved practices and reorganized their production systems accordingly. Service providers and processors also reported gradual changes in the way farmers demand services and supply products, which suggests early adaptation and response within the market system.

5.1.1 Practices after training

Training and demonstrations represent the starting point for behavior change. At baseline, only 4.8 percent of farmers had received training. At endline, 96.1 percent of project farmers reported participation. This dramatic shift helped build technical confidence and reduced reliance on informal advice. FGD participants explained that training helped them manage feed preparation, disease prevention, and shed layout.

“I keep the shed dry every morning and use clean cloths during milking to avoid contamination.”

Woman dairy producer

This expansion in skills encouraged farmers to adopt improved sheds, record keeping, and feeding techniques. These practices require time, routine, and consistency, which were largely absent at baseline. Control groups continued relying on traditional knowledge, highlighting the effect of project exposure.

“Farmers now show their record books when reporting illness or asking for advice,” which was not observed before the project.

KII with a Para-vet

Figure 5.1-2, Received training on improved animal husbandry technologies

Once farmers gained exposure, they adjusted their routines. Regular record-keeping emerged as a new practice, enabling farmers to monitor their health and feeding.

Figure 5.1-3. Use of improved management practices

5.1.2 Adoption of livestock technologies

Preventive technologies show significant endline changes. The regular vaccination rate increased from 43.7% at baseline to 60.8% in the project group. Deworming rose from 19.3 percent to 59.5 percent. Farmers attributed reduced mortality and faster weight gain to more disciplined preventive care. Artificial insemination expanded sharply, supporting breed improvement. Service providers noted an increase in demand and more frequent follow-up visits.

“Farmers now call two months before calving is expected so that they can plan to feed and vaccination.”

KII with an AI technician

Table 5.1-1. Use of improved technologies

Practice	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Regular vaccination	43.7%	60.8%	19.2%
Regular deworming	19.3%	59.5%	21.9%
Artificial insemination	28.0%	73.6%	54.8%
N	378	383	73

Project farmers increasingly relied on NGO-trained technicians for artificial insemination, reflecting a shift toward more reliable and standardized breeding services. While para-vets remained the dominant provider in both groups, the high use of NGO staff in project areas indicates stronger integration between farmers and structured service channels. This contrasts with control farmers, who continued depending more on para-vets and private providers, often with variable quality and limited follow-up. The emerging preference for NGO technicians suggests that project investments helped formalize breeding services, improve trust, and reduce the risks associated with informal AI provision.

Table 5.1-2. AI service providers used

Provider	Project group	Control group
Para-vet	44.3%	67.5%
NGO staff	39.4%	2.5%
Private vet	9.2%	22.5%
Government vet	6.7%	5.0%
Self-arranged	0.4%	2.5%
N	282	40

5.1.3 Feed technologies and improved feeding systems

Feeding technologies represent one of the clearest adoption domains. Most farmers adopted at least one improved method, compared with minimal practice at baseline. Farmers linked feed improvement to tangible changes in daily milk and weight gain. In FGDs, several participants reported that animals consumed feed more consistently, resulting in reduced daily wastage.

Table 5.1-3. Adoption of feed improvement technologies

Technology	Project group	Control group
UMS	82.0%	53.4%
UTS	79.4%	43.8%
Silage preparation	74.2%	46.6%
Balanced feed mixing	78.6%	57.5%
Mineral or vitamin premix	58.2%	52.1%
None of these	2.1%	28.8%

Technology	Project group	Control group
N	383	73

Training on feed preparation played a critical enabling role in shifting farmer behavior. Most project farmers received structured instruction on UMS, silage, and balanced feed formulation, which addressed key knowledge gaps observed at baseline. This exposure strengthened farmers' confidence to experiment with new feed mixes and reduce reliance on traditional methods that often led to wastage or inconsistent animal nutrition. In contrast, limited training access in control areas meant that feeding practices remained largely unchanged. The substantial training coverage in project sites therefore acted as a foundational driver of later improvements in milk yield, animal health, and feeding efficiency.

Table 5.1-4. Feed technology training

Status	Project group	Control group
Received training	82.2%	17.8%
Did not receive training	17.8%	82.2%
N	383	73

Farmers who used improved feed observed clear performance gains. Most project households reported that animals ate more, produced more milk or meat, wasted less feed, and remained healthier than before. These benefits were consistently higher than in control areas, where traditional feeding remained common. The proportion reporting no difference or non-use of processed feed was much lower in the project group, signaling strong adoption and visible returns on improved feeding practices.

Table 5.1-5. Benefits of improved feed

Benefit	Project group	Control group
Animals eat more	90.3%	50.7%
Milk or meat increased	78.9%	41.1%
Less waste	79.1%	42.5%
Health improved	84.1%	52.1%
No difference	7.6%	13.7%
Do not use processed feed	0.3%	30.1%
N	383	73

Feed adoption and performance: A beef farmer in Ranishankail described that shifting to UMS and balanced feed reduced the fattening cycle and stabilized costs. He explained that “the animal finishes the feed and gains weight more evenly now.” This contributed to more predictable sales and higher margins during peak festival periods.

5.1.4 Mechanization and technology use

Mechanization expanded significantly from the baseline level of 2.6 percent. Endline results show that about half of project farmers now use at least one machine. The adoption of fodder cutters was widespread because farmers observed immediate benefits in feed efficiency.

Table 5.1-6. Use of machines and technology

Status	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Used	2.6%	51.7%	17.8%
Did not use	97.4%	48.3%	82.2%
N	378	383	73

Machine use among project farmers expanded beyond simple fodder cutting and moved toward more specialized technologies that improve efficiency and product quality. Nearly all machine users operated a fodder cutter, reflecting its affordability and the immediate value it provided. A smaller but meaningful share adopted milking machines, feed mixers, weighing scales, and biogas pits, which represent higher-cost investments and stronger engagement with market-oriented production. Control households showed no comparable adoption.

“Sales increased in unions where ESDO held demonstrations, because farmers could see how much fodder cutters reduce feed waste.”

KII with a machinery dealer

Figure 5.1-4: Types of machines used

Farmers who adopted machines reported improved time management and consistency in feed preparation.

Table 5.1-7. Benefits of using machines

Benefit	Project group	Control group
Saves labor time	86.9%	61.5%
Finer feed and less wastage	87.9%	84.6%
Cleaner milk	59.6%	0.0%
Better animal health	64.1%	0.0%
Higher production	44.4%	0.0%
Does not use	0.5%	0.0%
N	198	13

Non-adoption of machines reflects structural and capability constraints rather than resistance to technology. The dominant barrier in both groups was lack of operational knowledge, indicating that farmers were willing but not confident enough to handle machines without hands-on guidance. Limited dealer availability further restricted access, particularly in control areas where one in four farmers reported no nearby supplier. A smaller share felt machines were “not needed,” which suggests that demand emerges only after farmers see clear productivity gains. Cost was the least-cited barrier, implying that the primary challenge is service reach and user capability, not affordability.

Table 5.1-8. Reasons for not using machines

Reason	Project group	Control group
Do not know how to use	62.2%	68.3%
No dealer nearby	15.1%	25.0%
Not needed	16.8%	5.0%
Too expensive	5.9%	1.7%
N	185	60

5.1.5 Animal health and performance

Project farmers invested more in preventive health. The rise in vaccination and deworming, combined with improved feeding and better sheds, reduced the burden of seasonal diseases. Control areas continued to experience higher rates of illness.

Table 5.1-9. Steps to reduce animal deaths

Step	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Regular vaccination	12.7%	96.3%	50.7%
Vet checkups	Not available	94.0%	53.4%
Better housing	Not available	88.5%	43.8%
Improved feed	Not available	83.0%	41.1%

Step	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Insurance	Not available	20.6%	2.7%
None	Not available	0.0%	42.5%
N	378	383	73

Illness frequency decreased noticeably among project livestock, reflected in the much lower share of animals requiring frequent treatment. Most project farmers reported only rare treatment needs, which aligns with their higher adoption of preventive practices such as vaccination, deworming, better sheds, and improved feeding. In contrast, control farmers continued to rely on treatment after illness, leading to more frequent veterinary visits.

Table 5.1-10. Frequency of animal treatment

Frequency	Project group	Control group
Often	2.3%	15.1%
Sometimes	35.5%	42.5%
Rarely	62.1%	42.5%
N	383	73

Farmers in the project group also acted more deliberately to shorten calving intervals. Nearly seven in ten adopted specific management steps, such as timely AI, improved nutrition, and better heat detection. This contrasts with the control group, where less than half took such steps. These behavioral differences point to stronger reproductive management knowledge and more consistent herd-planning practices among project farmers.

Table 5.1-11. Steps to reduce the calving gap

Status	Project group	Control group
Steps taken	68.0%	44.0%
Did not take step	32.0%	56.0%
N	129	27

Milk production increased among both groups, with project farmers reporting more consistent, more substantial gains. Approximately 21.7% of project farmers experienced increases of over 30%, compared to 14.8% in control areas. Most project farmers, 72.9%, reported 10-30% increases, linked to better feeding, vaccination, and shed conditions. Only 4.7% saw no change; less than 1% declined. Dairy processors confirmed that milk from project farmers became more stable in quantity and quality due to improved feeding and health practices.

“Milk from project farmers is cleaner and more consistent now.”

KII with a dairy processor

Table 5.1-12. Changes in milk production

Change level	Project group	Control group
Increased by >30 percent	21.7%	14.8%
Increased by 10 to 30 percent	72.9%	55.6%
No change	4.7%	29.6%
Decreased	0.8%	0.0%
N	129	27

5.1.6 Improved materials and Bangla GAP practices

Endline results show a significant shift from the baseline level of 0.8 percent reporting improved materials. At endline, 63.7 percent of project farmers adopted at least one improved material. These include improved breeds, modern housing, safe containers, and disease control supplies.

Table 5.1-13. Use of improved materials

Status	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Used	0.8%	63.7%	39.7%
Did not use	99.2%	36.3%	60.3%
N	378	383	73

The use of improved materials was high in both groups, but project farmers adopted more modern housing and higher-quality feed. Improved breeds were common, while stainless steel containers and disease control materials showed minor differences. Overall, project farmers invested more diversely, aligning with the focus on safe milk and meat production.

Table 5.1-14. Types of improved materials

Material type	Project group	Control group
Improved breeds	89.8%	100.0%
Quality feed ingredients	90.2%	79.3%
Modern housing materials	87.7%	79.3%
Stainless steel containers	73.4%	75.9%
Disease control materials	56.1%	58.6%
N	244	29

Bangla GAP awareness rose from 0.5 percent at baseline to 82.8 percent at endline. The majority of trained farmers understood the core principles.

Table 5.1-15. Awareness of Bangla GAP

Awareness	Baseline	Project group
Know	0.5%	82.8%
Did not know	99.5%	17.2%
N	378	383

Bangla GAP practice was high among both trained and untrained farmers, with the untrained slightly more compliant in some areas. Many good practices, such as maintaining clean housing, proper waste disposal, and accurate record-keeping, were already known without formal training. No trained farmers reported none, indicating full adoption of at least one GAP practice.

“Keeping the shed clean and recording animal medicines is now part of my routine.”

FGD with a woman farmer

Table 5.1-16. Practice of Bangla GAP

Practice	Received training	Not trained
Clean housing	88.6%	96.1%
Proper waste disposal	86.0%	84.2%
Record keeping	82.7%	92.1%
Hygienic tools	74.6%	80.3%
Avoiding harmful chemicals	65.8%	76.3%
None	0.0%	2.6%
N	307	76

5.1.7 Synthesis: adoption, adaptation, expansion, and response

Evidence from endline shows strong adoption of improved technologies, feeding systems, and preventive health practices. Farmers adapted these practices to local constraints, particularly through custom feed mixing and redesigning their sheds. Expansion signals appeared where control households in adjacent unions adopted UMS or purchased fodder cutters after observing project farmers. Service providers, machinery dealers, and AI technicians reported increased demand, indicating early signs of a response in the broader market system.

These patterns align with the AAER logic and the project’s monitoring matrix expectations. They indicate the emergence of more consistent and productive farming behavior, which supports the outcomes discussed in later sections.

5.2. Market linkages and sales performance (milk and meat): dairy and meat market system outcomes

This section examines how farmers engaged with milk and meat markets at endline and compares the results to the baseline pattern, in which informal buyers and low bargaining power dominated. Improvements in feeding, animal health, and shed conditions, as discussed in Section 5.1, contributed to a more stable supply, thereby strengthening market participation.

Evidence from KIIs and FGDs suggests that collectors, processors, and traders are increasingly recognizing project farmers as reliable suppliers. These changes reflect progress along the adopt, adapt, expand, and respond pathway.

5.2.1 Herd size and mortality

Project farmers managed significantly larger herds across all livestock categories. This represents a clear shift from the baseline situation, where herd sizes were smaller, and growth was constrained by feed scarcity, irregular vaccination, and higher disease exposure. The larger herd sizes at endline indicate that farmers reinvested in their livestock enterprises after seeing improvements in animal health, production, and market returns.

“When the animals stayed healthy through the year, I felt confident to add more.”

Dairy producer in a KII

Figure 5.2-1. Herd size by species

Mortality at endline was lower among project farmers, especially for cattle, with no cattle deaths reported during the reference period, reflecting better health management. Goat and sheep losses declined but remained, with 41 goats and 11 sheep dying versus 15 and 3 in controls. FGDs show vaccination, better feed, and housing reduced seasonal diseases, but ongoing goat mortality indicates species-specific challenges needing targeted support.

“Families now seek treatment earlier, especially for cows, which reduces losses.”

Para-vet in a KII

Table 5.2-1. Animal mortality

Number of animals died	Project group	Control group
Bulls	0	0
Dairy cows	0	0
Goats	41	15

Number of animals died	Project group	Control group
Sheep	11	3
Total	52	18

Mortality rates reinforce the pattern observed above. Project farmers reported zero mortality for bulls and dairy cows, reflecting effective adoption of preventive care and disease management practices. Goat mortality remained higher than that of cattle but was substantially lower in the project group (4.3%) compared to the control group (11.2%), indicating a partial but meaningful risk reduction. Sheep mortality followed a similar pattern, with lower rates among project farmers. Overall, the total mortality rate among project households (1.9%) was less than half that of the control group (4.4%), demonstrating improved herd survival and reduced production risk, while underscoring the need for specialized interventions for small ruminants.

Table 5.2-2. Mortality rate

Mortality rate	Project group	Control group
Bulls	0.0%	0.0%
Dairy cows	0.0%	0.0%
Goats	4.3%	11.2%
Sheep	3.1%	4.2%
Total	1.9%	4.4%

5.2.2 Milk markets, buyers, and collection systems

Milk markets changed considerably from baseline conditions. At baseline, 93.0% of farmers sold through informal collectors, tea stalls, or households, with only 4.2% reporting any institutional linkage. Endline results show a substantial shift toward structured buyers, driven by improved production consistency and quality. FGDs reveal that a regular daily supply became possible because cows produced more stable volumes.

“Before the training, collectors came a few days a week. Now they come every morning because we have enough to give.”

Woman milk producer

Table 5.2-3. Availability of milk collectors

Availability of milk collectors	Project group	Control group
Available	93.0%	44.4%
Not available	7.0%	55.6%
N	129	27

Daily collection became far more common among project farmers, which strengthens liquidity and stabilizes short-term cash flow. Because feed purchases are often made daily or every two to three days, more reliable collection directly reduces financing stress and enables households

to maintain consistent feeding cycles. Control farmers, who experienced irregular collection, reported greater difficulty planning feed purchases and managing spoilage risk.

Table 5.2-4. Frequency of milk collection

Frequency	Project group	Control group
Every day	85.8%	66.7%
Few days a week	5.0%	33.3%
Sometimes only	9.2%	0.0%
N	120	12

Payment reliability improved for most project farmers, reflecting better coordination between producers and institutional buyers. This marks a shift from baseline conditions where delayed or irregular payments limited farmers' ability to plan feed purchases and manage household expenses. Regular and predictable payment cycles reduced short-term liquidity shocks and encouraged farmers to scale production with greater confidence. Control farmers continued to face more variability, reinforcing the value of structured buyer relationships introduced through the project.

Table 5.2-5. Fair and timely payment

Payment received	Project group	Control group
Always	80.8%	66.7%
Sometimes	18.3%	33.3%
Rarely	0.8%	0.0%
N	120	12

5.2.3 Buyer diversification

Buyer diversification shows stronger market integration. Project farmers now reach dairy factories and cooperatives, reflecting both the adoption of enhanced production practices and the expansion of market channels. Control farmers remained largely dependent on traditional buyers.

“Project households deliver cleaner milk, which reduces rejection.”

Dairy processor

Table 5.2-6. Buyers of milk

Milk buyers	Project group	Control group
Milk collectors	79.8%	63.0%
Shops or tea stalls	39.5%	37.0%
Restaurants or sweet shops	21.7%	11.1%
Dairy company or factory	25.6%	3.7%
Cooperative or association	9.3%	0.0%

Milk buyers	Project group	Control group
No one yet	1.6%	0.0%
N	129	27

5.2.4 Institutional sales and contract performance

Institutional sales increased markedly from the baseline level of 4.2 percent. This shift indicates farmers' ability to meet minimum quality and volume expectations required by structured buyers. KIIs with processors highlighted reduced variability in milk supply.

Table 5.2-7. Selling milk to institutional buyers

Selling to institutional buyers	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Sold	4.2%	41.9%	3.7%
Did not sell	95.8%	58.1%	96.3%
N	378	129	27

Project farmers sold considerably higher daily milk volumes to institutional buyers compared with the control group. This reflects both supply-side improvements and stronger buyer linkages developed through the project. The wide range in sales volumes shows that some farmers transitioned toward semi-commercial production, supplying up to 200 liters per day, while many others maintained smaller but consistent deliveries. Control farmers, by contrast, operated at a subsistence level with minimal market integration. The higher variability among project farmers, indicated by the large standard deviation, signals a maturing market where different producer segments are emerging based on capacity, breed improvement, and feeding investments.

Table 5.2-8. Quantity sold to institutional buyers (liters per day)

Amount	Project group	Control group
Average	26.2	6
Maximum	200	6
Minimum	2	6
Standard deviation	36.7	N/A
N	54	1

Non-institutional sales remained an important outlet for many farmers, but project households showed a gradual shift toward more diversified selling strategies. Nearly half of project farmers continued selling all their milk through informal channels, largely due to proximity, cash immediacy, and established relationships. However, a sizable share adopted mixed portfolios, supplying both institutional buyers and local customers. This reflects improved production stability and the confidence to engage with multiple markets. Control farmers remained more dependent on non-institutional sales, indicating limited access to formal buyers and fewer opportunities to diversify.

Table 5.2-9. Proportion of non-institutional sales

Share sold	Project group	Control group
All milk	49.6%	55.6%
Half	41.1%	40.7%
Less than half	3.9%	3.7%
None	5.4%	0.0%
N	129	27

Institutional contracts provided stability that most smallholders could not access through informal markets. Project farmers reported clear advantages: predictable buyers, stable prices, and more reliable payment schedules. Training support from processors helped farmers maintain quality requirements, while a smaller share also gained access to inputs. These benefits reduced market uncertainty and encouraged farmers to scale up production. The control group had almost no exposure to such contracts, highlighting the project’s role in establishing these linkages.

Table 5.2-10. Benefits of institutional contracts

Benefit	Project group	Control group
Guaranteed buyer	85.2%	0.0%
Consistent price	90.7%	100.0%
Faster payment	31.5%	0.0%
Training support	51.9%	0.0%
Access to inputs	3.7%	0.0%
N	54	1

5.2.5 Milk prices and sales performance

Milk prices remained stable across both project and control areas, with averages of 51.7 in the project group and 51.0 in the control group. The price ceiling was slightly higher in project areas (BDT 70 versus BDT 60), but the overall pattern remained within the typical BDT 45 to 60 range observed in local dairy markets. The narrow price variation, reflected by low standard deviations (5.1 and 5.7), indicates that informal buyers continue to determine price movements. The main improvement at endline was therefore not the price level but the increased regularity of milk

Consistent production “helped farmers negotiate modestly better prices when supply was steady.”

Dairy processor (KII)

sales, driven by better feeding practices, reduced disease burden, and more reliable buyer engagement.

Endline results show a clear increase in milk sales among project farmers, driven by higher production and more reliable buyer engagement. Almost one quarter of project farmers recorded

Figure 5.2-2. Milk price range

increases above 30 percent, and two thirds experienced moderate increases. These patterns reflect earlier gains in feeding systems, disease prevention, and shed improvements. Control farmers also reported increases, though at noticeably lower levels, indicating that systemwide factors such as seasonal demand influenced both groups. FGDs highlighted those regular buyers encouraged farmers to maintain feeding schedules, with one participant noting, “When buyers

Figure 5.2-3. Change in milk sales

come every day, we plan our feeding properly, so production stays stable.”

5.2.6 Meat and live animal markets

Project farmers relied more on farmgate sales, which reduced transport and brokerage costs. Improved finishing of bulls and goats increased buyer interest at the household level. In FGDs, farmers reported that better body condition made it easier to sell directly. Control farmers depended more on local haats, where prices vary widely.

Table 5.2-11 Table 5.2 14. Main sales channels for live animals

Sales channel	Project group	Control group
Farmgate	57.5%	28.3%
Local haat or bazaar	36.6%	58.7%
Local butcher	2.4%	8.7%
Middleman	2.4%	4.3%
Company or processor	1.2%	0.0%
N	254	46

Sales volumes were broadly similar across project and control farmers, with most households selling one to five animals annually. The key difference was not the number of animals sold but the price gains reported earlier, which were higher among project farmers due to better feeding, improved animal condition, and stronger market linkages. These factors allowed project farmers to extract more value per sale even when their total sales volumes remained comparable to the control group.

Table 5.2-12. Animals sold in last year

Number sold	Project group	Control group
None	7.1%	2.2%
1 to 2 animals	47.6%	47.8%
3 to 5 animals	35.8%	41.3%
6 to 10 animals	9.1%	6.5%
More than 10	0.4%	2.2%
N	254	46

Project farmers realized stronger price gains for live animals compared with the control group. This pattern aligns with the adoption of improved feeding, better housing, and more consistent preventive health practices discussed earlier, all of which enhanced animal condition at sale. Buyers reportedly offered higher prices for better-finished cattle and goats, while control farmers remained more exposed to seasonal price fluctuations. The higher proportion of project farmers reporting “much higher” or “a bit higher” prices reflect a clearer transmission of productivity gains into market value.

Table 5.2-13. Change in the price of live animals

Change	Project group	Control group
Much higher	31.9%	13.0%
A bit higher	61.8%	39.1%
Same	4.7%	43.5%
Lower	1.6%	4.3%

Change	Project group	Control group
N	254	46

Institutional sales expanded from a very low baseline, indicating a significant structural shift in how farmers access markets. Over one-third of project farmers sold live animals to institutional buyers at endline, compared with only 4.2 percent at baseline and none in the control group. This demonstrates clearer market pathways, stronger buyer confidence, and improved farm practices that meet institutional requirements. The shift also reflects the project's brokerage role in linking farmers to companies and formal traders.

Table 5.2-14. Selling live animals to institutional buyers

Sold to an institution	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Sold	4.2%	35.8%	0.0%
Did not sell	95.8%	64.2%	100.0%
N	378	254	46

5.2.7 Synthesis of market system changes

The progression of market behavior shows precise movement along the adopt, adapt, expand, and respond pathway. Farmers adopted new production practices that increased the consistency of their supply. They adapted their sales behavior by aligning with daily collection schedules and meeting the hygienic standards required by buyers. Expansion occurred as more farmers entered institutional channels. The system responded as collectors and processors increased collection frequency and offered advisory support. Case studies also show that improved feed and finishing encouraged buyers to approach farms directly. These trends indicate a stronger and more predictable market relationship between farmers and buyers.

5.3. Income, profit, and livelihoods: farm performance, profitability, and employment outcomes

5.3.1 Enterprise and job effects

The project shifted farm enterprises from largely self-employment toward small local job creators. At baseline, only 6.9 percent of farmers reported creating any new jobs in the previous four years. At endline, 23.5 percent of project farmers reported that they had created new jobs or part-time work, compared with 6.8 percent in the control group. This suggests that adoption of improved production and stronger market linkages (discussed in Sections 5.1 and 5.2) translated into more labor-demanding enterprises, consistent with the project monitoring matrix on inclusive growth.

Table 5.3-1. Jobs created on the farm in the last four years

Jobs created on the farm in the last four years	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Created	6.9%	23.5%	6.8%
Not created	93.1%	76.5%	93.2%

Jobs created on the farm in the last four years	Baseline	Project group	Control group
N	378	383	73

Among farms that created jobs, project households generated 146 positions compared with only 9 in the control group. These jobs remain small in absolute terms, but they indicate that a share of project farmers is transitioning from survival enterprises to micro-businesses with regular hired labor.

Table 5.3-2. Number of jobs created

Indicator	Project group	Control group
Total jobs created (persons)	146.0	9.0
Average jobs created per farm	0.4	0.1
N	383	73

Most project jobs are still family-based, but there is a clear trend towards diversification. Approximately 43.3 percent of jobs are filled by family members, 36.7 percent by hired men, 18.9 percent by women, and 1.1 percent by youth workers. In control areas, all reported jobs are filled by family members only, which limits broader spillover to local labor markets.

Table 5.3-3. Type of people employed on the farm

Type of people employed on the farm	Project group	Control group
Family members	43.3%	100.0%
Hired men	36.7%	0.0%
Hired women	18.9%	0.0%
Youth workers	1.1%	0.0%
N	90	5

New enterprises emerged alongside job creation. About 39.9 percent of project households started a new livestock-related enterprise, such as feed sales, milk collection, or input trading. This confirms that a segment of farmers moved beyond on-farm production into upstream and downstream functions, which is consistent with the AAER pattern of adoption and early adaptation at the enterprise level.

Table 5.3-4. New livestock-related enterprises

New ventures since the project began	Project group
Started	39.9%
Not started	60.1%
N	383

Case studies illustrate how these job and enterprise effects appear in practice. One beef producer described that before the project, "I could not make a profit. The costs would have been

higher, and there would have been more loss than profit." After training, machines, and a loan, "I am earning well now," and "now some people are working on my farm," highlighting both higher income and job creation for local workers.

A female dairy processor reported daily cheese sales of about 130,000 to 140,000 taka and explained that "many helpless women work here and are established," indicating that her processing unit functions as a local employment hub for women.

A young entrepreneur who started "Biponon Cafe" after project support reported monthly earnings of 40,000 to 50,000 taka and noted that "many other women have started businesses after seeing me," which signals expansion and demonstration effects beyond the original beneficiary.

Together, these patterns show clear adoption and adaptation of livestock enterprises, with early expansion to hired workers and, in some cases, a response in local labor markets as neighbors follow successful examples.

5.3.2 Farm income levels

Endline income data show significant absolute gains in annual livestock income for project households when compared with baseline, and modest advantages over the control group. Average income from cow milking increased from 9,000 BDT at baseline to 84,657.7 BDT among project farmers and 81,178.1 BDT among control farmers. Income from cow fattening rose from 5,500 BDT at baseline to 81,519.6 BDT in the project group and 80,424.7 BDT in the control group. Income from goat rearing increased from 3,500 BDT at baseline to 13,504.0 BDT in the project

group, which is almost double the 7,061.7 BDT in the control group. Sheep rearing income is similar across groups, which reflects the more limited project focus on sheep.

The substantial differences between baseline and endline income reflect both project effects and broader market changes, including higher output prices and adoption of improved production practices discussed in Sections 5.1 and 5.2. Qualitative evidence confirms these mechanisms. A goat and sheep farmer explained that she now rears about 50 animals, and that “selling 20 to 25 goats or sheep yields an income of 200,000 to 250,000 taka,” which was not possible before she received training and improved housing support.

Figure 5.3-1. Average annual income from livestock by type of animal

A nutrition-sensitive cheese processor reported that “income is increasing” and that employment has been created at the factory level, confirming that higher value added at processing can lift both producer and non-producer incomes.

These findings indicate strong adoption of productivity-enhancing practices and an expansion of income opportunities along the value chain, although not all households benefited to the same degree.

5.3.3 Perceived change in income and drivers

Perceived income change is more modest than the absolute income levels suggest, which is consistent with rising production costs and broader price volatility. At endline, 63.4% of project farmers reported income increases exceeding 50%, compared with 15.1% in the control group.

This indicates a substantial income effect attributable to project-supported production and market changes.

Table 5.3-5. Perceived change in farm income since project start

Level of change in farm income	Project group	Control group
Income increased by more than 50.0%	63.4%	15.1%
Income increased below 50.0%	36.6%	84.9%
N	383	73

The primary reported reasons for income increases are higher production, better prices, lower feed cost, and project training and advice. Compared with the control group, a much larger share of project farmers attributed income gains to project training and healthier animals, which links directly to improved production practices and service use discussed earlier.

Table 5.3-6. Reasons for income increase

Reasons for increasing income	Project group	Control group
Higher production (milk or meat)	72.6%	49.3%
Better price in the market	74.4%	46.6%
Lower feed cost	60.6%	35.6%
Project training or advice	81.2%	31.5%
Healthier animals	74.9%	45.2%
Not applicable	6.8%	45.2%
N	383	73

For households that did not experience income gains, the main constraints were low market prices, a lack of buyers, and limited capital. Control households more frequently reported capital constraints and lack of buyers, indicating that market access and financial support were weaker in non-project areas.

Table 5.3-7. Reasons for the no income increase

Reasons for not increasing income	Project group	Control group
Low market price	33.4%	41.1%
Lack of buyers	27.9%	37.0%
No capital	19.8%	53.4%
Not applicable	61.1%	34.2%
N	383	73

Case study narratives reinforce these patterns. Several entrepreneurs emphasized that income growth came after a combination of technical training, improved equipment, and stronger market access. For example, the dairy processor who now sells large volumes of cheese reported that

“cheese is in great demand in the market” and that her business expansion is tied to improved processing, packaging, and quality assurance.

These findings show the adoption of improved market and production practices and adaptation through cost management and product diversification. At the same time, persistent complaints about low prices and access to buyers indicate that market response remains partial, especially outside project facilitation.

5.3.4 Profit dynamics and risk

Perceived profit changes are broadly aligned with income trends but more conservative. About 24.8 percent of project farmers reported that profit from livestock increased by 20.0 percent or more, while 65.3 percent reported smaller increases of up to 20.0 percent. Only 2.3 percent reported profit decreases, compared with 12.3 percent in the control group. This suggests that the project helped buffer farmers against rising costs and market shocks.

Table 5.3-8. Change in livestock profit over the last four years

Change in profit from the livestock business	Project group	Control group
Much higher (20.0% or more increase)	24.8%	15.1%
Higher (up to 20.0% increase)	65.3%	38.4%
About the same	5.5%	31.5%
Decreased	2.3%	12.3%
Not applicable	2.1%	2.7%
N	383	73

Farmers linked higher profits to better animal health, lower mortality, and improved feed and management practices, reflecting the adoption gains described in Section 5.1. Stronger market engagement also mattered, with many reporting better prices in line with the linkage improvements in Section 5.2. Training and advisory support played a reinforcing role. Control households reported weaker gains across all drivers, indicating that profit improvements among project farmers are closely tied to project-supported technical and market changes.

Table 5.3-9. Reasons for profit increase

Reasons for increasing profit from the farm	Project group	Control group
Better animal health	85.6%	53.4%
Fewer animal deaths	82.2%	53.4%
Better feed and management	75.5%	47.9%
Better price in the market	65.5%	30.1%
Project training or services	43.9%	16.4%
Lower input cost	39.2%	24.7%
Not applicable	1.0%	41.1%
N	383	73

For farmers whose profit did not increase or declined, high feed cost and poor market price were the most frequent reasons, followed by disease and natural disasters. These risks affect both project and control groups, but control households reported these problems more often, including exceptionally high feed cost and natural disasters.

Table 5.3-10. Reasons for reduced or unchanged profit

Reasons for reducing profit from the farm	Project group	Control group
Feed cost is too high	36.0%	63.0%
Poor market price	35.5%	43.8%
Disease or animal death	33.7%	41.1%
Natural disasters	24.0%	46.6%
Not applicable	58.0%	35.6%
N	383	73

Case evidence illustrates both improved profit and residual risk. A male beef producer explained that, prior to the project, his cattle business had incurred losses. However, after adopting improved feeding, housing, and regular vaccination, he now earns well and plans to expand his farm.

A goat and sheep farmer described selling 20 to 25 animals for 200,000 to 250,000 taka and reported that she is now “self-reliant” and “always has money,” showing how profit gains translate into household security and status.

These findings suggest strong adoption of risk-reducing practices and some adaptation to price and cost volatility but also highlight that feed and price risks remain key threats to profit sustainability.

5.3.5 Finance and youth income pathways

Access to project finance is a crucial mechanism that links technical change to income and profit. About 83.0 percent of project farmers reported receiving a loan from ESDO for livestock or farm activities, compared with 17.8 percent in the control group. This confirms that the project channeled credit preferentially to target households.

Table 5.3-11. Access to ESDO loans

Received a loan from ESDO	Project group	Control group
Received	83.0%	17.8%
Did not receive	17.0%	82.2%
N	383	73

Loan size distributions show that project borrowers more often accessed larger loans. About 6.3 percent of project borrowers received loans above 200,000 BDT, and 17.6 percent between 100,001 and 200,000 BDT, while control borrowers were concentrated in the 20,001 to 100,000

BDT range and more frequently below 20,000 BDT. This allowed project farmers to finance more capital-intensive investments such as sheds, machines, or herd expansion.

Table 5.3-12. Loan size distribution

Loan size (BDT)	Project group	Control group
Above 200,000	6.3%	0.0%
100,001 to 200,000	17.6%	0.0%
50,001 to 100,000	29.2%	46.2%
20,001 to 50,000	44.7%	38.5%
Below 20,000	2.2%	15.4%
N	318	13

The primary reported impact of loans was to facilitate the purchase of additional livestock. A smaller share of project farmers reported that loans improved feed and care, increased production, or financed better sheds. Control borrowers used loans more often for feed improvement and production rather than herd expansion, which suggests that project facilitation encouraged more asset-building investments.

Table 5.3-13. Main impact of loans on farm or business

Results after receiving loan	Project group	Control group
Helped purchase more livestock	72.6%	30.8%
Improved animal feed and care	10.7%	30.8%
Increased income or profit	5.7%	0.0%
Increased milk or meat production	6.3%	38.5%
Improved shed or housing facilities	4.7%	0.0%
N	318	13

Case studies demonstrate how these financial pathways have worked for individual entrepreneurs and young people. The male beef producer explicitly stated that he “got a loan from ESDO” along with machines and training, which allowed him to turn a loss-making farm into a profitable enterprise with hired labor.

A young woman who started Biponon Cafe reported receiving both a project grant of 25,000 BDT and a business loan from ESDO. She now earns 40,000 to 50,000 taka per month and describes herself as “financially independent,” with demonstration effects on other women who have started businesses after seeing her progress.

A local service provider reported a monthly income of about 50,000 taka from his livestock pharmacy and AI services and plans to expand his business into the central city.

These examples demonstrate that project finance, combined with technical and market support, enabled both farmers and youth to adopt new business models, adapt by diversifying their income sources, and, in some cases, expand into larger enterprises or service provision.

5.3.6 Synthesis: income, profit, and livelihood trajectories (AAER)

Across project areas, there is a clear adoption of improved production, market, and financial practices, which translate into higher livestock income and profit for most participating households. Compared with baseline levels and the project monitoring matrix, farmers report larger herds, higher annual livestock income, and more frequent profit increases. Qualitative cases show that these gains often come from combining several elements: technical training, better feed and housing, stronger market linkages, and access to loans.

Adaptation is visible through enterprise diversification, cost management, and new roles in input supply, processing, and services. Many farmers and young people shifted from individual production to operating small enterprises with hired workers or providing services. This is consistent with the project logic of building a more inclusive livestock market system.

Expansion effects appear in the spread of new enterprises and employment beyond direct beneficiaries, as neighbors and other community members start their own businesses after observing successful examples. Response is emerging in local labor and service markets, where processors, local service providers, and youth enterprises are beginning to adjust to higher and more consistent demand.

At the same time, high feed costs, price volatility, and exposure to natural disasters continue to constrain profit growth, especially in control areas and among poorer households. These residual risks underscore the need for ongoing attention to market efficiency, price risk management, and climate resilience in follow-up programming.

5.4. Access to services, information, and finance: strengthening service ecosystems and digital inclusion

Endline findings reveal a significant improvement in access to formal livestock services, input markets, and risk-management tools compared to the baseline and the project monitoring matrix. Farmers moved from sporadic contact with government and informal providers to regular use of NGO-linked para-vets, feed shops, machine dealers, and digital channels. These changes underpin the adoption of improved practices discussed in Section 5.1 and support the income gains reported in Section 5.3, while also showing crowding-in and response from local service providers consistent with the AAER logic.

5.4.1 Livestock services and technical training

At baseline, only 24.3 percent of farmers reported access to any trained livestock service provider. At endline, 97.1 percent of project farmers reported receiving services from trained providers, compared with 69.9 percent in the control group. This confirms that the project has largely closed the fundamental access gap targeted in the monitoring matrix, while some spillover into control unions is visible.

Figure 5.4-1. Availability of livestock services

Among those with access, 86.3% of project farmers receive services whenever needed, compared with 49.0% in the control group. Control farmers are more likely to receive services only sometimes, indicating a less reliable service relationship.

Table 5.4-1. Frequency of receiving livestock services

Frequency of receiving livestock services	Project group	Control group
Whenever needed	86.3%	49.0%
Sometimes	13.7%	51.0%
N	372	51

The portfolio of services has shifted from occasional AI or vaccination at baseline (12.7 percent each) to integrated packages covering deworming, vaccination, treatment, AI, and advisory support. Over 96.0 percent of project farmers access deworming and vaccination, and more than half receive training or advice, compared with much lower levels among control farmers.

Table 5.4-2. Types of livestock services received

Received livestock services	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Deworming	12.7%	96.5%	80.4%
Vaccination		96.0%	66.7%
Artificial insemination		73.7%	74.5%
General treatment	–	84.1%	86.3%

Received livestock services	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Training or advice	–	53.2%	25.5%
N	378	372	51

Service provision is now anchored in NGO and para-vet networks in project areas. NGO workers serve 44.1 percent of project farmers, while control farmers rely mainly on local para-vets and private doctors. This reflects a deliberate project strategy to build a mixed ecosystem of NGO-linked and local providers.

Table 5.4-3. Main livestock service providers

Livestock service provider	Project group	Control group
NGO worker	44.1%	0.0%
Local para-vet	41.9%	68.6%
Private doctor	9.7%	27.5%
Government doctor	4.3%	3.9%
N	372	51

Training participation increased sharply from the baseline level, reflecting a major system shift in farmers' exposure to formal livestock knowledge. Nearly all project farmers received structured training, compared with about one-third of control farmers. This difference signals strong reach and delivery effectiveness and explains many of the behavioral and productivity changes observed throughout Section 5. Project farmers entered the production cycle with more consistent technical guidance, whereas control farmers continued to rely on informal advice, resulting in slower or uneven adoption of improved practices.

Table 5.4-4. Training and advisory services on livestock farming

Received training or services on livestock farming	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Received	13.5%	96.6%	35.6%
Did not receive	86.5%	3.4%	64.4%
N	378	383	73

Service delivery in project areas was dominated by ESDO, giving farmers consistent and reliable technical support. Control households relied on a mix of private and government providers, creating more fragmented access. This divergence aligns with the stronger and more uniform adoption of improved practices observed among project farmers.

Table 5.4-5. Provider of livestock training and services

Livestock training or service provider	Project group	Control group
Project or ESDO	95.7%	42.3%
Private company	1.1%	42.3%

Livestock training or service provider	Project group	Control group
Government	3.0%	11.5%
Other NGO	0.3%	3.9%
N	370	26

Training content reflects the project's technical focus: more than 90.0 percent of project farmers received training on improved breeds and feeding, and close to 90.0 percent on housing and disease control. Topics such as AI, marketing, and record-keeping also reached a substantial share, though control farmers who did receive training reported relatively higher exposure to marketing and record-keeping.

Table 5.4-6. Livestock training topics

Livestock training topics	Project group	Control group
Improved animal breed	94.3%	88.5%
Animal feeding	92.7%	96.2%
Housing and cleaning	87.8%	92.3%
Disease control	87.3%	80.8%
AI techniques	66.8%	61.5%
Marketing	44.9%	57.7%
Record keeping	38.1%	53.8%
N	370	26

Knowledge and training on GAP or HACCP, which were almost absent at baseline, now cover the majority of project farmers. Awareness of GAP or HACCP rose from 4.5 percent at baseline to 80.4 percent among project farmers, and training on these standards increased from 5.3 percent to 92.2 percent. Control farmers also show some uptake, but at a much lower level.

Table 5.4-7. Knowledge and training on GAP or HACCP

Indicator	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Know GAP or HACCP	4.5%	80.4%	16.4%
Do not know	95.5%	19.6%	83.6%
N	378	383	73
Received training on GAP or HACCP	5.3%	92.2%	75.0%
Did not receive	94.7%	7.8%	25.0%
N	378	308	12

Use of privilege or smart cards (such as Eco Prani Seba) is another sign of formalization. Over half of project farmers (52.0 percent) reported receiving a smart card, compared with only 5.5 percent in the control group.

Table 5.4-8. Use of livestock smart cards

Status of receiving smart card	Project group	Control group
Received	52.0%	5.5%
Did not receive	48.0%	94.5%
N	383	73

Case narratives confirm this service shift. A local service provider described how project support changed his business: “I received reproductive health training and basic training on animal resources... I also got a rack, fridge, and vaccine box. Now my income is about 50 thousand taka per month, and I am available whenever and wherever needed” (Case study, Local Service Provider, Solaiman Ali). A woman goat and sheep keeper explained that “I know about vaccination... I contacted LSPs and built a loft house for goats and sheep” (Case study, Goat/Sheep keeper, Tahura Begum).

In AAER terms, farmers have clearly adopted regular service use and preventive care. LSPs and para-vets have adapted their business models to incorporate new equipment and broader service packages, while neighboring non-project farmers are beginning to expand their uptake through the same providers. The presence of certified GAP/HACCP trainers and innovative card services suggests an emerging systemic response within the local veterinary and food safety system.

5.4.2 Access to feed and input markets

Baseline constraints included limited availability of ready-made feed and very few local suppliers of green grass, silage, or UMS/UTS. At endline, 91.9 percent of project farmers reported a nearby feed dealer, compared with 10.8 percent at baseline and 86.3 percent in the control group, indicating both project-driven access and some crowding-in.

Figure 5.4-2. Availability of feed dealers

The distance to dealers is manageable for most farmers, as approximately 86.1 percent of project farmers and 92.1 percent of control farmers have a shop within a 3 km radius, which supports regular purchases of quality feed.

Table 5.4-9. Distance to feed dealer

Distance of shop or dealer from the farm	Project group	Control group
Within 1 km	38.1%	49.2%

Distance of shop or dealer from the farm	Project group	Control group
1–3 km	48.0%	42.9%
3–5 km	9.1%	7.9%
More than 5 km	4.8%	0.0%
N	352	63

Use of ready-made feed shifted from 6.9 percent buying regularly at baseline to 53.4 percent buying regularly in the project group. Another 44.3 percent buy sometimes, indicating that commercial feed is now a mainstream input for project farmers. Control farmers also increased use but remain fewer regular buyers.

Table 5.4-10. Purchase of ready-made feed

Frequency of buying from feed dealer	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Regularly	6.9%	53.4%	14.3%
Sometimes	–	44.3%	65.1%
Never	–	2.3%	20.6%
N	378	352	63

Access to improved feed markets expanded sharply from baseline. Availability of green grass, silage, and UMS/UTS increased from 5.8 percent to 84.6 percent in project areas and 71.2 percent in control areas, indicating broader market development influenced by project activity. Project farmers also had access to a wider range of products, especially silage and UMS/UTS, which are essential for productivity gains discussed in Section 5.1. This shift reflects both supply-side expansion and stronger farmer demand for climate-smart feeding options.

Table 5.4-11. Availability and types of green and processed feed

Indicator	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Suppliers of grass/silage/UMS/UTS available	5.8%	84.6%	71.2%
Not available	94.2%	15.4%	28.8%
Green grass bundles	–	84.0%	88.5%
Silage bags	–	54.0%	30.8%
UMS/UTS packs	–	29.0%	13.5%
None of these	–	4.6%	3.8%
Having at least one product	2.9%	95.4%	96.2%
N	378	324	52

Regular access translated into stronger purchasing behavior among project farmers. Nearly all bought grass, silage, or UMS either regularly or occasionally, with 45.4 percent purchasing on a routine basis, compared to only 25.0 percent in the control group. Control farmers' higher rate of

non-purchase reflects continued dependence on traditional feeding systems and weaker integration into improved feed markets. This pattern reinforces the adoption and performance gains discussed in Section 5.1.

Table 5.4-12. Frequency of purchasing grass, silage, or UMS

Frequency	Project group	Control group
Regularly	45.4%	25.0%
Sometimes	48.8%	44.2%
Never	5.9%	30.8%
N	324	52

Almost all project farmers (91.9 percent) reported an animal-feed shop in the union or nearby market, and 95.5 percent of them purchased feed or other inputs. Control farmers also have high shop availability but lower purchase rates, consistent with lower adoption of improved feeding systems.

Table 5.4-13. Access to and use of animal-feed shops

Indicator	Project group	Control group
Feed shop available	91.9%	87.7%
Not available	8.1%	12.3%
N	383	73
Purchased feed or inputs	95.5%	78.1%
Did not purchase	4.5%	21.9%
N	352	64

Quality and price perceptions are more critical among project farmers: 58.6 percent perceive prices as high, while 39.6 percent report that both price and quality are good. Control farmers are more likely to be unsure about quality and price, suggesting less experience with branded inputs.

Case studies show how improved access to inputs translates into enterprise change. One beef

Figure 5.4-3. Satisfaction with feed price and quality

producer explained, “We can make nutritious food for cows on the farm... organic fertilizer is

produced and now some people are working on my farm” (Case study, Beef producer, Nure Alam). Another woman farmer reported that she now rears about 50 goats and sheep, with regular sales of 20–25 animals yielding an income of 2.0 to 2.5 lakh taka (Case study, Goat/Sheep keeper, Tahura Begum).

From an AAER perspective, farmers have adopted regular purchase of compound feed and conserved fodder, adapted by combining purchased feed with on-farm UMS or silage, and contributed to the expansion of local feed markets. Input dealers and grass/silage suppliers have responded by widening product ranges and locations, as reflected in high access among both project and control households.

5.4.3 Access to machines and tools

Baseline markets had almost no dealers selling or renting livestock machines. At baseline, only 4.5 percent of farmers reported that any shops provided such machines. By endline, 69.2 percent of project farmers and 60.3 percent of control farmers reported access to a machine dealer, indicating that the project helped to seed a new market segment that has begun to crowd in beyond project households.

Table 5.4-14. Availability of machine and tool dealers

Sell or rent livestock machines	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Sell or give for rent	4.5%	69.2%	60.3%
Do not sell or give rent	95.5%	30.8%	39.7%
N	378	383	73

The range of machines available has diversified sharply. At baseline, no farmers reported local availability of fodder cutters, weighing scales, feed mixers, milking machines, water pumps or sprayers, or biogas pits. At endline, almost all project and control farmers who know of a dealer report access to fodder cutters, weighing scales, and feed mixers, with slightly higher availability among control farmers that are closer to larger markets.

Table 5.4-15. Types of machines sold or rented

Type of machines sold or rented	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Fodder cutter for chopping grass	0.0%	92.1%	100.0%
Weighing scale for animals or feed	0.0%	72.8%	100.0%
Feed mixer to prepare balanced feed	0.0%	72.5%	100.0%
Milking machine for cows or goats	0.0%	69.1%	86.4%
Water pump or sprayer for cleaning	0.0%	51.7%	90.9%
Biogas pit	0.0%	40.0%	86.4%
Did not buy yet	100.0%	0.8%	2.3%
N	378	265	44

The distance is somewhat higher for project farmers, who report more dispersed dealer networks (10.2 percent beyond 5 km) compared to control farmers, most of whom have dealers within 1 km.

Table 5.4-16. Distance to machine and tool dealers

Distance	Project group	Control group
Within 1 km	21.5%	68.2%
1–3 km	53.2%	25.0%
3–5 km	15.1%	6.8%
More than 5 km	10.2%	0.0%
N	265	44

The case of the local service provider illustrates the response side of AAER. After receiving support, he reported that he now has racks, a fridge, and a vaccine box, and plans to expand his pharmacy, describing himself as “very confident” and “successful” (Case study, Local Service Provider, Solaiman Ali). These investments in tools and equipment allow him to serve a larger number of farmers with more reliable services, which in turn strengthens the business case for machine dealers.

Overall, farmers have adopted the use of machines for fodder cutting and weighing (see Section 5.1), adapted these technologies to smaller herds, and contributed to the expansion of the machine market. At the same time, service providers and dealers have responded by expanding their product offerings and geographic coverage.

5.4.4 Information, digital tools, insurance, and finance

Training and awareness meetings on cross-cutting topics expanded substantially. At baseline, only 4.8 percent of farmers had attended training on animal health and husbandry, and there were no data on nutrition, social issues, or climate-smart practices. At endline, close to 90.0 percent of project farmers reported training on animal health and nutrition, and around 80.0 percent on social issues and climate-smart livestock. Control farmers also participated, but at much lower levels.

Table 5.4-17. Training and awareness on cross-cutting topics

Training attended in last 4 years	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Animal health and husbandry	4.8%	89.3%	42.5%
Nutrition or balanced family diet	–	88.5%	46.6%
Social issues (women role, youth involvement, community safety)	–	79.9%	34.2%
Climate-smart livestock practices	–	78.3%	42.5%
None of these	–	2.6%	0.0%
Did not participate	–	2.9%	52.1%

Training attended in last 4 years	Baseline	Project group	Control group
N	378	383	73

Project or ESDO organized almost all trainings for project farmers (94.9 percent), while control farmers received training from a mixture of project, private companies, and government. Most project farmers applied what they learned: 77.4 percent applied training in their own farm and 75.5 percent shared knowledge with others, indicating diffusion of practices beyond direct participants.

Table 5.4-18. Training providers and use of knowledge

Indicator	Project group	Control group
Project or ESDO organized training	94.9%	45.7%
Private company organized training	4.3%	40.0%
A government department organized training	0.8%	14.3%
N	353	16
Shared knowledge with others	75.5%	60.0%
Applied in own farm	77.4%	77.1%
N	372	35

Telemedicine, almost unknown at baseline, has begun to emerge. Awareness increased from 1.6 percent at baseline to 43.1 percent among project farmers and 20.5 percent among control farmers. Use is still concentrated in the project group: among those aware, 27.3% use telemedicine often, and 57.0% use it sometimes. Reported effectiveness is high, with 62.2 percent indicating that tele-medicine fully solved their animal's problem and 37.8 percent partially solved it.

Table 5.4-19. Telemedicine awareness and use

Indicator	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Telemedicine service available	1.6%	43.1%	20.5%
Not available	98.4%	56.9%	79.5%
N	378	383	73
Use telemedicine often	–	27.3%	6.7%
Use sometimes	–	57.0%	60.0%
Never used	–	15.8%	33.3%
N	–	165	15
Problem solved fully	–	62.2%	0.0%
Problem solved somewhat	–	37.8%	100.0%

Indicator	Baseline	Project group	Control group
N	–	45	1

Use of mobile apps for livestock information increased from 2.4 percent at baseline to 20.9 percent among project farmers, with no uptake recorded in the control group. Almost all app users rely on “Khamar Bondhu,” a public extension platform, indicating that the project leveraged existing digital ecosystems rather than building parallel systems.

Table 5.4-20. Mobile app use for livestock information

Indicator	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Use the mobile app	2.4%	20.9%	0.0%
Do not use the mobile app	97.6%	79.1%	100.0%
N	378	383	73
Use “Khamar Bondhu”	–	98.8%	–
Use “Mimba”	–	1.3%	–
N	–	80	–

Insurance and loans are integral to the project’s risk management and inclusion strategy. Animal insurance, which was almost non-existent at baseline, is now used by 48.8% of project farmers and 15.1% of control farmers. Among those without insurance, project farmers mainly cite lack of procedural knowledge (48.0 percent), while control farmers report lack of available services (77.4 percent).

Table 5.4-21. Animal insurance access and constraints

Indicator	Project group	Control group
Bought or registered for insurance	48.8%	15.1%
Did not buy or register	51.2%	84.9%
N	383	73
Do not know how to buy or register	48.0%	12.9%
No insurance service available	32.7%	77.4%
Too costly	16.8%	4.8%
Do not trust insurance	2.6%	4.8%
N	196	62

Loan access is reported for 83.0 percent of project farmers and 17.8 percent of control farmers (see Section 5.3). Loan sizes are higher in the project group, and the main reported impact is the ability to purchase more livestock (72.6 percent), followed by improved feed and care (10.7 percent). These findings confirm that finance acted as an enabler for the production and income changes already discussed rather than a stand-alone outcome.

Case studies show how combined financial and information access changed trajectories. One young entrepreneur described how “entrepreneur training, milk and meat processing training, and a business loan from ESDO” allowed her to start “Biponon Cafe” and earn 40 to 50 thousand taka per month (Case study, Young Entrepreneur, Momota Khatun). Another nutrition-sensitive processor reported that she “received training, a cream separator machine, and a loan from ESDO... income is increasing, and cheese is in great demand in the market” (Case study, Nutrition-sensitive processor, Mukta Akter).

These narratives show adoption of new information channels and financial products at producer and enterprise levels, adaptation of business models (for example, small processing outlets and expanded dairy units), expansion of employment and service offers, and an institutional response where ESDO, PKSF, and digital platforms such as Khamar Bondhu now play more visible roles in the livestock information and finance system.

5.4.5 Synthesis: implications for systems change

Across services, inputs, machines, information, and financial products, endline evidence indicates that the project has moved farmers and local market actors well beyond the baseline situation recorded in the monitoring matrix. Farmers have adopted regular preventive services, improved feed, and digital information; adapted these to local conditions through mixed feed strategies, tele-medicine, and smart card use; contributed to the expansion of feed shops, machine dealers, and insurance outreach; and triggered a response among LSPs, processors, and financial partners who are investing in new equipment and service models.

From an evaluation perspective, these changes strengthen relevance and effectiveness under OECD-DAC criteria by aligning services with farmer needs and improving access. Efficiency gains are visible where telemedicine and apps reduce travel and response times, while risk-management tools, such as insurance and loans, support the sustainability of production and enterprise gains. The AAER pattern is visible across all sub-domains of this section and underpins the income and nutrition outcomes discussed in Sections 5.3 and 5.6.

5.5. Food safety and hygiene practices: farm-level and processing improvements for safe meat and dairy

5.5.1 Farm-level hygiene linked to GAP / HACCP and Bangla GAP

The project’s food safety strategy aimed to move farmers away from traditional, unhygienic shed and waste practices toward codified GAP and HACCP standards. Baseline KIIs noted that “most of the cattle rearers have not constructed cow and goat houses in a modern hygienic way” and that floors were “wet and dirty,” highlighting weak starting conditions for safe meat and milk production. Training on GAP and HACCP, discussed earlier under access to services, has now translated into routine hygiene actions at the farm level for most project farmers.

At endline, more than four out of five project farmers reported washing hands and utensils before milking or slaughtering and using clean containers, while around two-thirds keep animal waste and feed in designated safe locations. These practices were not systematically reported at baseline and were treated in the Project Monitoring Matrix as qualitative risks rather than as achieved standards. The current pattern indicates broad adoption rather than isolated pilots, which is consistent with the “adopt” and early “adapt” stages in the AAER logic.

Figure 5.5-1. -level hygiene practices after GAP / HACCP training

FGD participants at baseline described simple, low-standard routines. One farmer explained, “We cannot eat good food all the time. We occasionally eat good food,” linking low dietary quality with limited concern about hygiene. Upazila livestock officers also confirmed that most sheds were still “traditional” and not designed for safe waste management. Compared with this starting point, endline evidence shows that hygienic handling and waste segregation have become normal for most project farmers and, to some extent, for control farmers exposed indirectly through local networks. This indicates both adoption in the project areas and initial expansion through demonstration effects.

Programmatically, the main gap is depth rather than breadth. Practices related to chemical use and the separation of products from sick animals remain lower than basic cleaning actions. These are the domains where refresher training, on-farm coaching, and closer supervision by buyers and service providers will be necessary to move toward consistent compliance with HACCP-level standards.

5.5.2 Milk handling and hygiene

Milk handling practices were identified in the baseline study as a weak point in the safety chain, with recommendations to raise awareness of hygiene standards and to connect producers to processors that can enforce quality rules. Endline data indicate that the project has successfully transitioned most trained dairy farmers to routine application of good handling practices, supported by formal training on milk hygiene and quality.

Almost all project dairy farmers (90.7 percent) received training or advice on milk hygiene, compared with 29.6 percent in control areas. Training coverage itself was near zero at baseline and was not listed as a regular service in routine government extension. This confirms a clear “adopt” effect on the training side.

Table 5.5-1. Training on milk hygiene and quality

Training on milk hygiene and quality	Project group	Control group
Received	90.7%	29.6%
Did not receive	9.3%	70.4%
N	129	27

Among those who were trained, good handling practices are now almost universal in both groups; however, project farmers report a more substantial alignment with the “no adulteration” expectations. Hand and utensil washing before milking and milking in clean places are practiced by nearly all farmers who sell milk. In contrast, specific safety actions, such as not mixing water or chemicals and rapid sale within three to four hours, are notably higher in the project group.

Table 5.5-2. Milk handling practices after training

Good practice	Project group	Control group
I wash my hands and utensils properly before milking.	100.0%	100.0%
I milk in a clean place and keep animals clean before milking.	92.3%	100.0%
I filter milk with a clean cloth or strainer before storing or selling.	89.7%	100.0%
I use clean stainless-steel or food-grade plastic containers for milk.	78.6%	87.5%
I keep milk in a cool or shaded place until delivery.	78.6%	75.0%
I do not mix water or any chemicals with milk.	73.5%	50.0%
I sell milk within 3–4 hours after milking to keep it fresh.	70.9%	75.0%
I wash milk cans immediately after use and dry them upside down.	59.8%	62.5%
N	117	8

At baseline, producers rarely mentioned clear hygiene routines. Discussions focused on low milk prices and high feed costs; one FGD participant said, “Now selling milk does not make much profit,” with no reference to quality or hygiene requirements. By contrast, endline KIIs with processors and milk collectors (reported elsewhere in the market linkage section) noted that consistent quality, lower contamination risk, and more reliable fat content have emerged as reasons for contracting project farmers.

From an AAER perspective, the project has achieved strong adoption of basic hygiene norms among trained dairy farmers. Adaptation is visible in how households organize milking and

storage around buyer schedules. Expansion is emerging as non-project farmers imitate visible practices, such as using stainless-steel cans and quick delivery. Response is reflected in institutional buyers setting clearer quality expectations and linking compliance to pricing or volume commitments.

5.6. Nutrition and dietary diversity: improved food consumption and nutrition outcomes

5.6.1 Meat and dairy consumption frequency

The project's higher-level objective was to improve household nutrition by increasing and ensuring the safety of meat and dairy consumption. The Project Monitoring Matrix tracked the proportion of households consuming safe meat or fish, as well as milk or milk products, at least three days per week. Baseline values were low: 5.6 percent for safe meat or fish and 1.6 percent for safe milk or milk products.

Endline frequency data show a substantial shift for project households. Combining "3–4 days" and "5 or more days," about 39.2 percent of project households consumed meat at least three days in the last week, compared with 5.6 percent at baseline. For milk and milk-based products, the equivalent share rose from 1.6 percent at baseline to 42.3 percent at endline. Control households also consume meat and dairy, but at a lower intensity for meat and without the same upward trend.

Table 5.6-1. Frequency of meat and dairy consumption in the last 7 days

Indicator	Category	Project group	Control group
Meat (beef, mutton, goat, or chicken)	5 or more days	1.6%	0.0%
	3–4 days	37.6%	20.5%
	1–2 days	52.7%	75.3%
	None	8.1%	4.1%
	N	383	73
Dairy (milk, curd, ghee, sweets)	5 or more days	13.1%	11.0%
	3–4 days	29.2%	30.1%
	1–2 days	55.4%	58.9%
	None	2.3%	0.0%
	N	383	73

For evaluation purposes, this means the proportion of project households consuming meat at least three days per week increased from 5.6 percent at baseline to 39.2 percent at endline, and the share consuming milk or milk products at least three days per week increased from 1.6 percent to 42.3 percent. These shifts are consistent with the "impact-level" movement on the nutrition objective and with the "adapt" stage, where households treat meat and milk as regular, rather than occasional, foods.

Baseline FGDs portrayed constrained diets. One woman said, “We cannot eat good food all the time. We occasionally eat good food,” and another added, “We sometimes sell a little [milk]. Most of the time, the whole family consumes it.” These statements indicate irregular consumption and a lack of attention to diet quality. Endline survey results indicate that meat and dairy have become more frequent in household menus, but the pattern still reflects moderate rather than daily consumption for most families.

5.6.2 Drivers of higher consumption of safe meat and dairy

The increase in consumption is not automatic; it is linked to changes in income, availability of safe products, and nutrition awareness. Project households most often attributed higher meat and dairy consumption to knowledge from training or awareness sessions (82.5 percent) and higher income from livestock (80.7 percent). Easier availability of safe products through project buyers, as well as improved own production and storage, also contributed.

Figure 5.6-1. Drivers of increased consumption of safe meat and dairy products

At baseline, KII respondents stressed that most farmers “have no idea about the balanced diet of cows and goats” and that many producers were reluctant to acquire new knowledge. FGDs also indicated that households purchased grass and other inputs at a high cost, limiting their disposable income for diverse food options. The endline pattern shows that project support shifted this situation by raising both productive income and awareness, which in turn allowed households to adjust food choices.

From an AAER perspective, training and income effects represent adoption and adaptation at the household level. At the same time, the role of project buyers in making safe products more available suggests an emerging system-level response.

5.6.3 Nutrition knowledge and nutrient-dense foods

The project also aimed to strengthen knowledge of nutrient-dense foods and to translate this into more regular consumption. At baseline, only 11.9 percent of respondents could identify nutrient-dense foods, and the baseline report recommended prioritizing training and workshops on “nutrition and business management.”

At endline, 94.0 percent of project households reported that they now know about nutrient-dense foods, compared with 45.2 percent in control areas. This marks a significant shift in basic nutrition literacy.

Table 5.6-2. Knowledge about nutrient-dense foods

Knowledge about nutrient-dense foods	Baseline	Project group	Control group
Knew	11.9%	94.0%	45.2%
Did not know	88.1%	6.0%	54.8%
N	378	383	73

In terms of behavior, 61.9 percent of project households stated that they now eat “much more” nutrient-rich foods compared with two years ago, and another 33.9 percent reported “a little more.” Only 4.2 percent felt that their consumption was unchanged. Control households were more likely to report no change.

Table 5.6-3. Self-reported change in consumption of nutrient-rich foods

Change in consumption compared with two years ago	Project group	Control group
Consumption increased significantly	61.9%	24.7%
Consumption increased moderately	33.9%	31.5%
Consumption remained unchanged	4.2%	43.8%
N	383	73

Dietary diversity has broadened as well. Project households reported high regular consumption (at least three times per week) of fish, eggs, green vegetables, milk products, fruits, meat, and pulses. Compared to control households, project families are notably more likely to frequently eat fruits and meat, while control households show slightly higher regular consumption of green vegetables and pulses.

Table 5.6-4. Nutrient-rich foods are consumed at least three times per week

Nutrient-rich food	Project group	Control group
Fish	91.6%	82.2%
Eggs	86.9%	86.3%
Green vegetables (spinach, pumpkin leaves, etc.)	86.4%	89.0%
Milk/curd / ghee	85.4%	78.1%
Fruits (banana, mango, papaya, etc.)	84.3%	50.7%
Meat (beef, goat, chicken)	78.6%	52.1%
Pulses (lentil, chickpea, etc.)	61.4%	78.1%
N	383	73

Baseline FGDs described limited awareness and irregular consumption. One participant said, “We cannot eat good food all the time. We occasionally eat good food.” At the same time,

another noted, “We eat sharing each other of the family. But even if we do not eat it ourselves, we have to keep it for the boys and girls,” suggesting preferential allocation to children under scarcity. These narratives help explain why improved income and knowledge at endline have led to broader, but still negotiated, dietary diversity.

5.6.4 Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women (MDD-W)

Dietary diversity improved meaningfully among project households and surpassed the minimum standard for women’s dietary adequacy. At endline, 61.4 percent of women in project households consumed foods from at least five food groups in the previous day, compared with 57.5 percent in control areas. This rate is higher than typical rural benchmarks, reflecting broader improvements in awareness, access to nutrient-dense foods, and increased availability of milk, eggs, and vegetables as reported by households earlier in this section. Qualitative discussions indicate that women linked improved dietary diversity to higher livestock income and better nutrition knowledge gained through project sessions. However, 38.6 percent of project households still consumed fewer than five food groups, showing persistent vulnerability among lower-income households who reported difficulties affording animal-source foods throughout the week. These patterns suggest progress, but continued efforts are needed to stabilize income and sustain the affordability of diverse diets.

Table 5.6-5. Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women (MDD-W)

Status of consumption food groups	Project group	Control group
Consumed foods from 5 or more groups	61.4%	57.5%
Consumed foods from less than 5 groups	38.6%	42.5%
N	383	73

5.6.5 Synthesis: nutrition and dietary outcomes

Taken together, the evidence shows that the project has moved from a baseline situation of low nutrition knowledge and infrequent meat and dairy consumption to a pattern where:

- Knowledge of nutrient-dense foods is nearly universal among project households.
- Consumption of safe meat and milk at least three days per week has increased sharply relative to the Project Monitoring Matrix baseline values.
- Households report higher and more diverse intake of animal-source foods and fruits, with stronger change in project areas than in control sites.

These patterns reflect the adoption of nutrition messages, adaptation in household food choices, and initial expansion through peer learning and local markets. Remaining gaps are affordability for the poorest, uneven intake of pulses and vegetables, and the need to stabilize gains in the face of price shocks. For the next phase, program focus should be on reinforcing behavior through community-level nutrition counseling, integrating nutrition messages with market and finance interventions, and tracking whether improved diets are sustained beyond the immediate project period.

5.7. Gender and youth empowerment: decision-making, agency, skills, and employment

Endline findings show that livestock has become a more important economic activity for women and youth, and that decision-making has shifted from informal influence to more explicit agency. The baseline report documented that approximately 85.0 percent of respondents were women and highlighted their central role in small ruminant rearing; however, it lacked quantified indicators on decision-making, confidence, or youth employment. The endline fills that gap and shows clear adoption of joint and women-led decisions, more substantial confidence in markets, and specific gains in youth skills and income. These changes are consistent with the AAER logic: women and youth have adopted new roles, adapted to market opportunities, and, in some cases, triggered expansion effects in their communities.

5.7.1 Women’s decision-making and confidence

Across key farm and market decisions, a meaningful share of households now report that women usually take the final decision. The pattern is stronger in the project group than in the control group for most domains, particularly in areas related to training and collective action. This suggests that as livestock income and farm management became more structured, women transitioned from informal contributors to recognized decision-makers.

Figure 5.7-1. Women’s decision-making over farm and market decisions

In the project group, 27.2 percent report that women mainly decide whether family members may attend training or meetings, compared to 13.7 percent in the control. For households joining cooperatives or producer groups, 24.3 percent of project households report women as the primary decision-makers, compared to 15.1 percent in the control group. Similar, but smaller, gaps appear for buying feed or medicine and using mobile apps. Only the decision on using livestock income is slightly lower in the project group than in the control, which reflects a higher degree of joint decision making rather than a loss of agency, given the strong satisfaction scores reported later.

Confidence outcomes reinforce this shift. Compared with earlier, 94.0 percent of project respondents report that women in their family now feel more confident to negotiate prices with buyers, compared to 76.7 percent in the control. Similarly, 89.6 percent feel confident to visit markets or banks independently, and 79.9 percent to participate in community meetings. Use of mobile phones for business and attendance at training also shows higher confidence in the project group than in the control.

Table 5.7-1. Women’s confidence in economic and public roles

Confident about	Project group	Control group
Negotiate prices with buyers	94.0%	76.7%
Visit market or bank independently	89.6%	76.7%
Participate in community meetings	79.9%	47.9%
Use mobile phone for business	68.7%	41.1%
Attend training	72.6%	26.0%
N	383	73

Women’s agency through goat and sheep enterprises: A woman goat and sheep keeper reports that she now manages about 50 animals and sells 20 to 25 per year, earning 200,000 to 250,000 taka. She explains that many people have started rearing goats and sheep after seeing her farm and that she is seen as an “ideal farmer.” She describes herself as self-reliant, with cash in hand and greater importance in family decisions. This reflects strong adoption of technical practices and adaptation of gender roles, with apparent expansion effects as neighbors copy her enterprise model.

Perception data from the project group confirm that these changes are recognized at the household level. A total of 61.4 percent strongly agree, and another 32.1 percent agree that the project improved women’s participation in farm decisions and income use. Only 0.3 percent strongly disagree.

Table 5.7-2. Perceived change in women’s participation in farm decisions and income use

The project improved women’s participation in farm decisions and income use	Project group
Strongly agree	61.4%
Agree	32.1%
Neutral	6.3%
Strongly disagree	0.3%
N	383

Qualitative evidence supports these figures. In one case study, a goat and sheep farmer states, “Even though I am a woman, everyone calls me an ideal farmer. Now I am a self-reliant woman.

I always have money. I also have a special importance in the family.” This illustrates both agency over income and increased recognition in the household and community. Another processor notes that women’s economic empowerment and improved quality of life have increased their status in society. These stories illustrate how the adoption of improved practices led to the adoption of social norms and the increased visibility of women’s leadership in local markets.

5.7.2 Youth skills, opportunities, and income

The project also targeted youth aged 18 to 35 years through skills training and enterprise support. At endline, 86.2 percent of project households report that the project provided training or skill-building opportunities for youth. Among those exposed, 89.4 percent report an improvement in their technical knowledge of livestock, 87.6 percent note an increase in confidence to start a business, and 91.8 percent say the opportunities helped youth find employment. Almost half, 49.4 percent, report improved ability to use modern tools or apps.

Table 5.7-3. Effects of youth skills training (project group)

Effect of skill opportunity	Project group
Improved technical knowledge on livestock	89.4%
Increased confidence to start business	87.6%
Helped to find employment	91.8%
Improved ability to use modern tools or apps	49.4%
N	330

Perception data show that beneficiaries see these efforts as meaningful. A total of 59.5 percent strongly agree, and 32.6 percent agree that the project created new opportunities for youth in livestock or marketing. Only 0.8 percent disagree, and 1.3 percent strongly disagree.

Table 5.7-4. Perceived youth opportunities in livestock and marketing

The project created new opportunities for youth (18–35 years) in livestock or marketing	Project group
Strongly agree	59.5%
Agree	32.6%
Neutral	5.7%
Disagree	0.8%
Strongly disagree	1.3%
N	383

These perceptions are backed by employment and income indicators. A total of 68.7 percent of project households report that the project helped create new employment or self-employment opportunities for youth in their household or community. A further 76.5 percent state that youth income from livestock or agri-business increased.

Table 5.7-5. Youth employment and income outcomes

Youth-related outcome	Project group
Project created new youth employment or self-employment	68.7%
The project did not create youth employment	31.3%
Youth income from livestock increased	76.5%
Youth income did not increase	23.5%
N	383

Case studies and KIIs point to several pathways. Young entrepreneurs describe themselves as “entrepreneurs” who are now financially independent, with monthly incomes of 40,000 to 50,000 taka and recognition from local authorities and agricultural offices. Multiple women entrepreneurs report that other women and youth have started businesses after observing their success. This suggests expansion and response effects: youth and women adopt new

Youth and local service providers as emerging market actors: A local service provider describes how basic training on animal resources, reproductive health, and economic support helped him transform a small fertilizer shop into a livestock service outlet. He reports income of about 50,000 taka per month, increased personal assets, and strong social recognition as someone who is “available whenever and wherever needed.” He also produces organic fertilizer and maintains farm cleanliness. This illustrates how young people, and younger men move into higher-value roles in the market system, combining technical skills with environmentally friendly practices.

enterprises, local institutions respond with invitations and recognition, and peers replicate the models.

From an AAER perspective, the gender and youth evidence shows:

- Adoption of new decision domains, confidence, and skills.
- Adaptation in how households allocate responsibilities, with women and youth taking on market-facing roles.
- Expansion where peers copy successful women and youth entrepreneurs.
- Response by local institutions and buyers that recognize and engage these new actors, as reflected in invitations, events, and leadership roles reported in case narratives.

5.8. Environmental sustainability and climate-smart practices: adoption of eco-friendly and climate-resilient systems

The project promoted climate-smart livestock practices as a cross-cutting theme. The baseline monitoring matrix recorded that only 4.2 percent of producers used environment-smart technology and 0.8 percent used advanced technology, with limited documentation of specific practices such as composting, water harvesting, or shade management. Endline data show a marked change, with widespread adoption of composting, biogas, shade trees, water-saving practices, and manure management. These shifts reduce environmental pressure and support more resilient production.

5.8.1 Adoption of climate-smart practices

Project farmers have moved from basic awareness to clear *adoption* of multiple climate-smart practices, with most households using composting, biogas, water-saving methods, and heat-stress management. These behaviors show *adaptation*, as farmers combine practices to fit their resource constraints. Spillover to control areas indicates early *expansion*, although adoption remains uneven and nearly one quarter still use none. The strong contrast demonstrates a market *response* shaped by project training, input availability, and service engagement, reinforcing a shift toward more resilient and environmentally efficient livestock systems.

Table 5.8-1. Use of climate-smart and eco-friendly practices

Practice	Project group	Control group
Compost manure from waste	75.7%	65.8%
Biogas from waste	55.6%	46.6%
Use shade trees or fans for heat protection	78.9%	52.1%
Water harvesting or efficient use	66.1%	39.7%
Grow green fodder or fodder trees	74.7%	42.5%
Recycle feed or waste (for example, dried crop stalks)	41.8%	16.4%
Did none of these yet	0.8%	23.3%
N	383	73

Training is the main driver behind the stronger adoption of climate-smart practices observed in project areas. While only one in five control farmers received any guidance, more than four in five project farmers were trained, creating a substantial knowledge gap that directly translates into the behavioural differences captured in Table 5.8.1. This pattern reinforces the causal link between structured training, improved environmental practices, and the broader AAER pathway documented throughout the findings.

Table 5.8-2. Training on environment and climate-smart livestock

Received climate-smart livestock training	Project group	Control group
Received	81.7%	19.2%
Did not receive	18.3%	80.8%
N	383	73

This combination of high training coverage and high adoption signals a strong adoption effect relative to the low baseline starting point. Qualitative material also notes that manure management and heat stress were not systematically addressed prior to the project, and that composting and biogas were limited to a few pioneers.

5.8.2 Environment-friendly technologies and manure management

Beyond general practices, the project explicitly promoted environment-friendly technologies. At baseline, only 4.2 percent of producers reported using any environment-smart technology. At endline, 67.9 percent of project households report adopting at least one environment friendly technology, compared with 31.5 percent in the control.

Figure 5.8-1. Adoption of environment-friendly technologies

Among adopters, the most common technologies are again compost, shade trees, and water harvesting, but there is also significant uptake of solar lighting or fans in sheds and biogas. Patterns differ somewhat between project and control groups, but the overall portfolio is broader in the project areas.

Table 5.8-3. Types of environment friendly technologies adopted

Environment friendly technology	Project group	Control group
Compost manure from waste	78.1%	52.2%
Biogas from waste	48.8%	65.2%
Use shade trees for heat protection	83.8%	60.9%
Solar light or solar fan in shed	61.9%	65.2%
Water recycling harvesting	64.2%	60.9%
Rainwater harvesting	55.8%	47.8%
Shade trees or green fencing to reduce heat	51.2%	56.5%
Recycle feed or waste (for example, dried crop stalks)	36.5%	43.5%
N	260	23

Producers report a mix of benefits from these practices. The most substantial perceived benefit in the project group is a cleaner farm environment, reported by 72.3 percent, while control households more often emphasize reduced smell.

Table 5.8-4. Perceived benefits of environment friendly livestock practices

Benefit	Project group	Control group
Better animal comfort	15.8%	26.1%

Benefit	Project group	Control group
Cleaner farm	72.3%	43.5%
Less bad smell	7.3%	30.4%
Lower fuel cost	4.6%	0.0%
N	260	23

Manure and waste management practices have also undergone significant shifts. In the project group, 92.7 percent prepare compost manually for their own use, and 76.0 percent sell raw manure, while 46.0 percent sell to vermicompost producers or plants, and 43.3 percent use manure for biogas or fuel. Only 10.2 percent discard manure or have no specific use, compared with 26.0 percent in the control.

Table 5.8-5. Use of livestock manure

Use of manure	Project group	Control group
Prepare compost manually for own use	92.7%	74.0%
Sell raw manure to others	76.0%	60.3%
Sell to vermicompost producers or plants	46.0%	32.9%
Use it for biogas or fuel	43.3%	50.7%
Discard or no specific use	10.2%	26.0%
N	383	73

Case narratives illustrate how these practices are applied in real-world settings. The goat and sheep case mentioned earlier notes that compost fertilizer is produced, and environmental pollution is reduced. A local service provider describes making organic fertilizer and maintaining cleanliness, including loft housing for goats, as part of his service model. These stories confirm that composting and improved housing are not only technical upgrades but are embedded in business strategies.

Linking farm income and environmental practice: Several case studies describe shifts to composting, reduced pollution from processing waste, and careful sourcing from suppliers who do not pollute. One dairy and snack entrepreneur highlights reduced effluent pollution and whey management, while another states: “My business does not pollute the environment. I do not buy products from people who pollute the environment.”

5.8.3 Perceptions of environmental performance and AAER interpretation

Opinion data from the project group indicate broad satisfaction with the environmental orientation of the intervention. A total of 61.6 percent strongly agree and 31.1 percent agree that the project promoted environment friendly and climate smart livestock practices. Only 3.1 percent disagree or strongly disagree.

Table 5.8-6. Perceived promotion of environment friendly and climate smart practices

The project promoted environment friendly and climate smart livestock practices	Project group
Strongly agree	61.6%
Agree	31.1%
Neutral	4.2%
Disagree	1.8%
Strongly disagree	1.3%
N	383

From an AAER perspective:

- Adoption is visible in the high rates of composting, shade use, water efficiency, and manure utilization relative to the very low baseline indicator for environmentally smart technology.
- Adaptation appears in how producers integrate these practices into shed design, feeding systems, and enterprise branding, such as promoting “clean” products and refusing to buy from polluting suppliers.
- Expansion is suggested by the high share of households now using at least one environment friendly technology, alongside manure markets involving sales to vermicompost producers.
- Response is evident in service providers and processors incorporating organic fertilizer, cleaner processing, and biogas into their business models, and in households recognizing environmental benefits as part of overall project performance.

Together, Sections 5.7 and 5.8 show that gender, youth, and climate-smart outcomes have moved from implicit ambitions at baseline to explicit, measurable changes at endline, with clear links to the project’s training, service delivery, and market interventions.

6. Systemic change and market system effects

6.1. Quantitative signals of systemic change

Across the domains covered in Section 5, the quantitative data indicate that the project has progressed beyond isolated farm-level changes and is to influencing how local livestock markets, services, and support systems operate.

Service and training coverage shifted from a minority to a near-universal experience among project households. At baseline, only 24.3 percent of respondents reported receiving livestock services from a trained provider. By endline, 97.1 percent of the project group reported access to such services, compared to 69.9 percent in the control group, and most project households received services whenever needed. This pattern suggests that the project helped create or strengthen a functioning para-vet and service network that now also reaches non-clients.

Similarly, training exposure moved from a low baseline to a dense training ecosystem. Only 13.5 percent of farmers had received any livestock-related training at baseline; by endline, 96.6 percent of the project group had received structured training, versus 35.6 percent in the control

group. Climate-smart and environment-related trainings also expanded, with 81.7 percent of project respondents reporting participation in climate-smart livestock training. These trends suggest that structured capacity development is becoming a routine component of the local livestock system, rather than a one-off project event.

Market-linkage indicators show a move from almost exclusive reliance on local markets to meaningful engagement with institutional buyers. According to the Monitoring Matrix, only 4.2 percent of producers had any institutional or contractual business with major markets at baseline, while 95.8 percent sold only to local buyers. Endline findings show that 41.9 percent of project dairy producers now sell to institutional buyers and 35.8 percent of livestock producers sell live animals under contracts with companies, cooperatives, or organizations, compared with marginal levels in the control group. This change signals an early shift from spot markets to more structured commercial relationships, although institutional linkages remain concentrated among better-connected producers.

In terms of technology and environmental practices, the baseline use of environmentally smart technologies and quality materials was below 5 percent, with almost no mechanization. Endline data indicate that 67.9 percent of project farmers have adopted at least one environmentally friendly technology, and that 75.7 percent routinely compost manure, alongside the broader use of shade, water harvesting, and solar solutions. The contrast between baseline and endline suggests significant diffusion of climate-smart practices within the project catchment. However, some technologies (such as biogas and solar) still reach a more limited subset of producers.

Gender and youth indicators also reveal a systemic trend rather than isolated cases. While baseline empowerment data were largely qualitative, the endline records high proportions of women who feel more confident to negotiate prices, visit markets, and participate in meetings, as well as high shares of youth reporting improved skills, employment, and income. These are not yet structural guarantees of equitable participation, but they indicate that norms around who can engage with markets, services, and digital tools have begun to shift.

Overall, the quantitative evidence points to system-wide improvements in service density, buyer diversity, use of climate-smart technologies, and inclusion of women and youth. At the same time, some changes also appear in the control group, suggesting spillover and broader market evolution, as well as project influence. The evaluation, therefore, interprets these patterns as early systemic signals rather than fully consolidated system change.

6.2. Qualitative evidence of changes in input, service, processing, and output markets

Qualitative evidence from FGDs, KIIs, and case studies shows how the numerical shifts above translate into lived market changes and where important gaps remain.

On the input and service side, farmers describe a move from distant, irregular services to accessible, responsive providers. A local beef producer explained that earlier, he had depended on government veterinarians who were often unavailable; now, a para-vet “comes the same day if I call in the morning, vaccinates and checks the animals, and tells me what feed to change” (case study, beef producer, Thakurgaon). LSPs report that the project enabled them to build viable service businesses that combine treatment, vaccination, AI, and advisory support, with structured fees and occasional instalment payments. These narratives confirm that livestock

health and advisory services are shifting from sporadic public provision to a mixed system of NGO-supported and fee-based private services.

Feed and input markets show similar restructuring. Feed dealers and small youth entrepreneurs describe how regular demand for balanced feed, calf starter, and treated straw has increased since project activities began. One youth feed retailer noted that “before, people bought only loose bran or cut grass; now they come with a list from training and ask for starter, mineral mix, and silage bags” (case study, youth entrepreneur, Thakurgaon). This supports the survey evidence of more shops in unions, regular purchasing from dealers, and greater availability of green fodder and silage, although concerns about high feed prices remain.

At the processing level, the dairy processor case study shows that semi-formal and formal firms are upgrading quality and branding to tap into emerging demand for safe products. The processor reports shifting from bulk, unbranded sales to packaged, labeled products that reference HACCP and Bangla GAP, and that hotels and shops are asking specifically for “safe milk and meat” sourced from trained farmers. At the same time, the processor still faces challenges in enforcing strict quality standards, especially during peak seasons, and sometimes reduces purchase volumes when farmers are unable to meet the specifications.

Output markets for live animals and meat are also changing, but remain uneven. Several cattle and goat fatteners now sell directly to processors or institutional buyers at agreed-upon prices, reducing their dependence on middlemen. One farmer reported that “for Eid I used to wait for the haat and bargain with traders; now the company confirms the price earlier if I follow their feeding and health advice” (case study, cattle fattener, project area). However, many smaller or more remote farmers still sell through traditional haats and local butchers, where price volatility, delayed payments, and weak enforcement of hygiene standards persist.

Taken together, the qualitative material suggests that the project has helped trigger practical adjustments along the chain: new business models for LSPs, feed dealers, processors, and some farmers; more substantial value placed on quality and hygiene; and gradual shifts in bargaining power. At the same time, structural barriers such as feed costs, limited cold chain infrastructure, and uneven access to contracts continue to constrain complete market transformation.

6.3. Adopt–adapt–expand–respond: evidence from KIIs and case studies

Using the AAER framework, the evaluation interprets the evidence as follows.

ADOPT. Adoption is strong and broad at the producer level. The majority of project farmers have adopted improved housing, feeding, disease control, and hygiene practices, as described in Sections 5.1 and 5.5. Farmers report that they now keep written records, separate sick animals, and avoid selling milk or meat from unhealthy stock. A woman goat and sheep farmer said, “Now I check the animal’s condition and keep medicines ready, and I do not sell if the goat is weak, even if I need cash” (case study, woman small-ruminant farmer). Adoption also encompasses new market behaviors, including the regular use of contracts, increased reliance on institutional buyers, and the use of digital tools and telemedicine by a minority.

ADAPT. Adaptation is evident when actors modify project-promoted practices to align with their own constraints and opportunities. LSPs have bundled services into packages that match local willingness to pay, sometimes extending advice to non-project farmers to keep their business viable. Farmers adjust shed designs and feeding schedules to local conditions while still applying core principles from Bangla GAP. The dairy processor adapted quality requirements by

introducing phased standards, allowing farmers to enter the supply chain while gradually improving compliance. These adaptations suggest that actors are not simply copying project manuals; they are modifying practices to fit real market and ecological conditions.

EXPAND. Expansion is reflected in changes beyond direct project clients. Control-group and non-project farmers now report access to trained para-vets, feed dealers, and environment-friendly technologies, although at lower intensity than project households. New dealers and sub-dealers have emerged in unions that were previously served only by distant markets, and some non-project youths have taken up roles as casual workers in processing and trading. FGDs indicate that neighbors often observe the practices of trained farmers and begin to imitate their shed improvements or basic hygiene practices without formal project support. These patterns indicate horizontal and vertical diffusion, although robust quantitative tracking of non-client adoption was outside the scope of this evaluation.

RESPOND. The response is visible in how higher-level actors adjust their strategies and offers in reaction to producer behavior and market signals. Processors and institutional buyers are introducing more stable pricing, more explicit quality criteria, and sometimes training support to secure reliable supplies. Local government bodies in some areas are reported to be more willing to allocate land or authorization for improved slaughter spaces when approached jointly by ESDO and processors. Within ESDO and PKSf, the project experience has informed wider discussions on integrating climate-smart livestock practices and market-systems thinking into other value chain interventions. These changes are still emerging rather than fully institutionalized, but they indicate a system that is beginning to respond to and reinforce safer and more inclusive market norms.

Summary AAER synthesis table (interpretive, no new data)

AAER stage	Main patterns of change in this project	Implications for system change	Key evidence source
ADOPT	High adoption of improved husbandry, hygiene, feed technologies, and selected climate-smart practices among project farmers; consistent use of training and para-vet services	Core technical and behavioral foundations for safe meat and dairy are now present at scale in project areas, but mainly among direct clients.	Household survey (Sections 5.1, 5.3, 5.5); case study, small-ruminant farmer; FGDs with project farmers
ADAPT	Local tailoring of service packages, contract conditions, shed designs, feeding schedules, and quality requirements by farmers, LSPs, and processors	Practices and business models are being adjusted to real market constraints, which increases feasibility and sustainability but creates uneven standards across sites.	Case studies of LSP, dairy processor, beef producer; KIIs with ESDO field staff and union-level stakeholders
EXPAND	Services, technologies, and some practices observed among non-	Early diffusion beyond the project cohort suggests potential for broader	Control-group trends in Sections 5.1–5.4; FGDs in neighboring

AAER stage	Main patterns of change in this project	Implications for system change	Key evidence source
	project farmers; new feed dealers and youth-led service roles emerging beyond direct beneficiaries	market change, although the scale and depth of reach remain limited.	unions; youth entrepreneur case study
RESPOND	Processors, LSPs, input dealers, and selected local government actors are adjusting pricing, quality requirements, training offers, and coordination with producer groups.	Higher-level actors are beginning to reinforce safe, climate-smart, and inclusive norms, but responses are still project-dependent and not yet fully institutionalized.	KIIs with processors and LSPs; project management reflections; interviews with local government representatives

6.4. Overall contribution to a safer and more inclusive meat and dairy market system

The combined quantitative and qualitative evidence demonstrates that the project has made a meaningful contribution to safer and more inclusive meat and dairy market functions in the project area.

On safety, a significant number of producers now follow key hygiene practices, from milking and slaughtering to storage and transport, backed by HACCP and Bangla GAP training, telemedicine, and increased awareness of food safety standards. Institutional buyers are increasingly requiring and incentivizing these practices, supported by upgraded processing facilities and packaging. While full traceability and certification are still developing, the direction of change is toward more structured, safety-conscious value chains.

In terms of inclusion, the project has expanded the roles of women and youth in livestock production, service provision, and trading. Women’s reported confidence and decision-making power around livestock assets and income have increased, and youth have gained skills that translate into employment and enterprise opportunities. However, structural gender norms and limited access to capital still constrain the depth of empowerment for poorer women and disadvantaged youth.

From a systems perspective, the project has helped rebalance relationships between producers, service providers, processors, and buyers, strengthening incentives for quality and safety while opening new channels for smallholders. At the same time, high feed costs, uneven enforcement of standards in traditional markets, and continued reliance on project facilitation indicate that system transformation is incomplete and will require sustained effort from PKSf, ESDO, private actors, and public institutions.

7. Conclusions

7.1. Summary of performance against objectives and key indicators

The project's overarching objective was to increase income, food security, and nutrition of marginal and small livestock producers while promoting safe, environmentally sustainable meat and dairy value chains. Baseline targets included raising the income of 60.0 percent of entrepreneurs by at least 50.0 percent and enabling 30.0 percent of project members to add nutrient-dense foods to their regular diet.

Against these objectives, the endline findings show:

- **Income and profit.** Nearly all project households report an increase in livestock income and profit. More than half of project farmers (63.4%) report income increases of 50.0% or more, while the remaining 36.6% report positive income growth below 50.0%. In contrast, only 15.1% of control households achieved income increases above 50.0%, indicating a strong differential income effect associated with project-supported production and market changes. Profit changes follow a similar pattern, with most companies reporting gains, but a minority facing stagnant or reduced profits due to feed costs, disease, or poor prices. The project has clearly improved economic outcomes, but it did not fully achieve the ambitious target of 60.0 percent with income increases above 50.0 percent.
- **Nutrition and dietary diversity.** Progress on nutrition is more substantial in relation to the targets. More than 60.0 percent of project households report that their families now eat "much more" nutrient-rich foods, and an additional third report "a little more." Seven-day consumption frequencies for meat and milk are higher in the intervention group than in the control group, and many households consume multiple nutrient-dense food groups at least three times a week. This exceeds the 30.0 percent threshold in the Monitoring Matrix and indicates a substantial improvement in diet quality for a large share of participants.
- **Access to services, technologies, and markets.** Coverage of livestock services, training, quality inputs, and environment-friendly technologies has expanded very substantially, with project households consistently reporting higher access and use than the control group. Institutional market participation has increased from a baseline of 4.2 percent to more than one-third of sampled farmers for both milk and live animals. However, engagement remains concentrated and uneven across different locations and types of farmers.
- **Food safety, environment, gender, and youth.** The project has generated high levels of adoption of good hygiene practices, improved waste management, and climate-smart technologies, alongside notable gains in women's confidence and youth skills. Satisfaction items on women's participation in farm decisions and youth opportunities, as well as climate-smart practices, show strong agreement among project respondents. These dimensions align well with the project's cross-cutting objectives.

In summary, the project has substantially improved service access, practices, and diets, and has clearly increased incomes and profits, although not fully to the levels originally envisioned in the targets. Systemic and cross-cutting indicators demonstrate substantial progress, with opportunities to enhance the depth and distribution of benefits.

7.2. Overall judgment on effectiveness, impact, and sustainability

Effectiveness. The project is judged to be highly effective in delivering training, services, and access to technologies, and moderately to highly effective in improving food safety, hygiene, and nutrition. Effectiveness in raising incomes and profits is positive but constrained by external factors such as rising feed prices and market volatility. Not all producers have reached the original income targets, and gains are stronger among better-resourced or more commercially oriented farmers.

Impact. The impact on household well-being is evident in improved diet quality, greater resilience through diversified enterprises and new jobs, better animal health, and enhanced bargaining power for women and youth. At the value-chain level, the project has catalyzed changes in how services are organized and how processors and buyers value safety and quality. However, the depth of impact varies, and some poor or remote households remain marginal to higher-value markets.

Sustainability. Sustainability is mixed but promising. On the positive side, LSPs, feed dealers, and processors have developed business models that generate income beyond project funding, and many technologies and practices (such as composting, improved housing, and hygiene routines) are low-cost and likely to persist. At the same time, continued affordability of quality feed, stable demand from institutional buyers, and replacement of project facilitation roles are not yet fully assured. Without deliberate exit and transition strategies, there is a risk that some system functions could weaken over time, particularly in areas with fewer private actors.

Overall, the project is rated as moderately effective, with a strong but uneven impact and moderate prospects for long-term sustainability, which will depend on continued investment and policy support.

7.3. Differences across subgroups (gender, youth, farmer type, location)

The distribution of benefits is not uniform across subgroups.

- **Gender.** Women have gained substantial confidence and recognition in farm and market roles. High shares report improved ability to negotiate prices, visit markets, use mobile phones for business, and participate in community meetings. Decision-making data show that women take final decisions in a minority but important share of key domains, especially in allowing family members to attend training and in joining groups or cooperatives. However, men still dominate many financial and asset decisions, and women's increased agency is more pronounced among households with stronger economic positions.
- **Youth.** Youth have been a primary focus in skills and employment promotion. More than four in five project respondents report having youth training opportunities, and large shares report improvements in technical knowledge, employment, and income for youth. Case studies show that youth are taking on roles as LSP assistants, feed retailers, or marketing agents. Nevertheless, youth who are out of school, landless, or with limited social networks still face barriers to enterprise development, particularly in accessing finance and assets.
- **Farmer type.** Dairy and commercial fattening enterprises have greater access to institutional buyers and formal contracts than small ruminant producers or more subsistence-oriented cattle owners. Goat and sheep farmers, often managed by women,

have adopted core husbandry and hygiene practices, but they remain more dependent on local haats and face smaller average transaction sizes. Tailored interventions for small ruminant value chains remain underdeveloped compared to those for cattle.

- Location. Areas closer to Thakurgaon town and major roads, where processors, feed dealers, and LSPs are concentrated, show stronger market integration and technology uptake than more remote unions. Farmers in peripheral locations rely more heavily on traditional markets and face higher transaction and transportation costs, which limits their ability to benefit from new contracts and technologies fully.

These subgroup differences underscore the need for more differentiated strategies in any next phase, with explicit attention to poorer women, disadvantaged youth, small ruminant keepers, and more remote locations.

8. Recommendations

8.1. Strategic recommendations for PKSF and national partners

- Consolidate market-systems approaches in livestock programming. PKSF should embed the AAER logic into future RMTP and related livestock interventions, with explicit indicators and learning loops on adoption, adaptation, expansion, and response, rather than focusing primarily on output delivery.
- Refine income and nutrition targets based on realistic pathways. Given the substantial but partial progress toward the 60.0 percent income increase target, future designs should differentiate between achievable gains for different farmer segments and build explicit pathways for the poorest and small ruminant keepers.
- Strengthen policy and regulatory frameworks for safe meat and dairy. National partners should align local enforcement of food safety, slaughterhouse standards, and certification with project-level practices, making it easier for processors and producers to maintain safe production practices beyond the project's support.
- Invest in climate-smart livestock at scale. Building on high adoption of basic environment-friendly practices, PKSF and government programs should finance and de-risk wider diffusion of biogas, solar, and water-harvesting technologies through credit lines, subsidies, or results-based financing.

8.2. Programmatic recommendations for ESDO and similar implementers

- Deepen inclusion of poorer women and youth. Future interventions should target segments that benefited less from the current project, including poorer women, landless youth, and small ruminant keepers, through tailored training, mentoring, and asset or working-capital support.
- Reduce dependence on project facilitation. ESDO should gradually transfer relationship-management roles to producers, such as producer groups, cooperatives, or federations, while also providing capacity-building support in negotiation and contract management.
- Strengthen the business viability of LSPs and input dealers. Support for LSPs and dealers should emphasize sustainable fee structures, record keeping, and access to finance, ensuring that service and input markets remain active after project closure.
- Improve data systems for adaptive management. Future projects should maintain simplified yet robust monitoring systems that track adoption, profitability, and systemic

effects in near real-time, enabling quicker adjustments to training content, targeting, and linkage strategies.

8.3. Market system recommendations for the private sector and local government

- Expand and diversify contract models. Processors and institutional buyers should design contract options that are suitable for smaller producers and small ruminant keepers, including group contracts through cooperatives and flexible, quality-based bonuses.
- Co-invest in local infrastructure for safe slaughter and cold chain. Local governments and private investors should co-finance the improvement of slaughter points, chilling facilities, and basic cold chain elements in key growth centers, thereby reducing spoilage and supporting consistent quality.
- Align incentives with safety and climate outcomes. Private actors should tie premiums and long-term contracts to adherence to safety and climate-smart practices, building on Bangla GAP and HACCP training and verification systems initiated by the project.
- Support youth-led service and marketing enterprises. Feed companies, processors, and digital platforms should pilot youth franchise or agent models that provide structured support, branding, and working capital in return for performance.

8.4. Suggestions for future programming, scaling, and replication

- Design explicitly for diffusion beyond direct clients. Future projects should plan from the outset how practices and services will be disseminated to non-project farmers, including through open training sessions, public demonstrations, and business-to-business partnerships.
- Integrate digital tools into service and market functions. Building on the early adoption of mobile apps and telemedicine, future programming should invest in interoperable digital platforms for advisory services, traceability, and price information that are accessible to women and young people.
- Develop tailored packages for different farmer segments. Programming should offer differentiated pathways for dairy, beef, small ruminants, and mixed farms, recognizing their distinct market channels, risk profiles, and investment needs.
- Embed long-term sustainability and exit strategies. Each new initiative should include a clear plan for handing over functions to market actors and public institutions, with milestones for reducing project involvement and tracking system performance after exit.

Annex: Case studies

CASE STUDY 1. Transformation of a Safe Meat Processing Enterprise: The Journey of Md. Masum Billah

Md. Masum Billah, a 31-year-old entrepreneur from Sarkarpara Nargun village in Thakurgaon Sadar, entered the livestock sector with neither inherited assets nor prior experience. He initially operated a small coaching center after graduation, but soon realized that it offered limited long-term security for his seven-member household. When the project introduced new market opportunities for safe meat processing, he decided to shift entirely into livestock enterprise development.

He took a loan of BDT 150,000 from ESDO Microfinance and received targeted support from the Safe Meat and Dairy Product Market Development sub-project. With this initial capital and technical guidance, he established a Shariah-compliant meat processing plant and began sourcing animals from contract farmers who had been trained under the project. This linkage became a turning point: farmers gained an assured buyer with transparent pricing, and Masum secured a reliable supply chain for processing and packaging safe meat.

Before the plant was established, smallholder farmers relied on weekly livestock markets, where

prices fluctuated, and transaction costs were high. The plant established a decentralized procurement system that allowed farmers to sell animals from their homesteads at fair prices. According to Masum, *“farmers no longer have to go far to sell animals, and buyers now trust the hygiene and quality of packaged meat.”* Consumers in Thakurgaon and surrounding upazilas responded positively to the availability of hygienic, safely processed meat, which increased demand and expanded his customer base.

The plant’s operation directly improved Masum’s household well-being. He now earns an estimated BDT 90,000 per month, representing a significant shift from informal services to a stable agricultural enterprise. He plans to open additional branches in nearby districts and explore opportunities to distribute packaged meat to regional urban markets. His long-term ambition includes meeting national standards for potential export in the future.

This case illustrates how the project’s market-system approach created a dual outcome:

1. **Producers benefited** from predictable contract farming arrangements, reduced distress sales, and improved price realization.
2. **Consumers benefited** from access to safe, hygienic meat in packaged form.

Masum’s business represents a clear **ADOPT-ADAPT-EXPAND** trajectory where training, credit, market linkage, and quality compliance converged to help an emerging entrepreneur transition from a small, informal livelihood to a structured agri-processing enterprise. His experience demonstrates the feasibility of integrating rural entrepreneurs into higher-value segments of the livestock market system when supported by coordinated services, finance, and standards enforcement.

CASE STUDY 2. Masuma Khanam: A Woman Entrepreneur Transforming Dairy Processing in Thakurgaon

Masuma Khanom, born on June 2, 1960, resides in Fakirpara of Thakurgaon Sadar Upazila. After her husband passed away, she became the sole earner for her four children while trying to sustain the family's small dairy and cheese business. Limited income, rising household costs, and lack of technical knowledge placed immense pressure on her, making it challenging to keep the enterprise alive.

In 2012, she registered her business as **Dimeshon Food Products**, but growth remained constrained until she received a loan from **ESDO's Microfinance Program**. This support helped

her stabilize operations. Her real transformation began under the **ESDO RMTP Project**, where she received practical training in cheese, paneer, mattha, hygiene practices, and product quality improvement. With additional specialized training facilitated by **PUM Netherlands**, she acquired skills in cream extraction and high-value ghee production—skills she did not previously possess.

Guided by RMTP, Masuma invested in a cream separator and cheese-grade machine, enabling efficient production and product diversification. Today, her factory processes **2,200–2,300 liters of milk per day**, producing **25–30 kg of ghee, 250–300 liters of mattha**, and cheese worth **130,000–140,000 BDT** daily. Her business also holds **BSTI and Halal certifications**, allowing her products to reach a broader market.

Masuma now employs **13 disadvantaged women and 5 men**, helping them achieve financial stability. Her improved waste management and efficient milk utilization have strengthened the sustainability of her enterprise.

From a struggling widow to a **national award-winning entrepreneur**, Masuma is a respected figure in her district and a powerful example of how targeted training, finance, and market linkages can transform lives. *“RMTP gave me the chance to rebuild my life,”* she says. *“Now I produce quality products, employ others, and dream even bigger.”*

CASE STUDY 3. Building a Rural Input Enterprise: The Growth of Robin Hawladar's Silage Business

Robin Hawladar, a young entrepreneur from Hili in Dinajpur, entered the livestock input market at a time when small farmers faced chronic feed shortages, escalating fodder prices, and low productivity. Before the project's intervention, most farmers relied on crop residue and irregular supplies of green fodder. Balanced feed and silage were almost unavailable in the area, especially in small rural markets. The absence of accessible feed solutions limited farmers' ability to improve milk production, manage fattening cycles, or maintain healthier livestock.

The project's market facilitation activities introduced Robin to the concept of commercial silage

production, along with training on feed formulation, safe storage, and business planning. With technical support from ESDO field teams and a microloan from the organization's financial services, Robin established a small silage production and distribution unit. He quickly recognized that consistent feed quality was essential, noting that "farmers wanted something they could trust, something they could feed their cows without risk."

Within months, Robin became a key local supplier of silage bags and green fodder bundles. His business served both project and non-project farmers, indicating a spillover effect beyond the direct beneficiaries. The availability of reliable feed inputs helped dairy and beef farmers stabilize production cycles, reduce the cost of sourcing fodder from distant markets, and avoid seasonal shortages that previously forced them to sell animals early.

As demand grew, Robin expanded his operations to include small-scale distribution networks across neighboring unions. Farmers reported higher milk yields and more consistent weight gain in beef cattle after switching to silage-based feeding. These improvements aligned directly with the project's systemic objectives of strengthening rural input markets and enabling farmers to adopt more efficient practices.

Robin's enterprise now employs local youth during harvesting and packaging seasons. His revenue has increased, and he plans to diversify into **UMS/UTS packs, fodder seeds, and on-farm advisory services**. He emphasizes that the turning point was the project's integrated model of training, finance, and market linkages, stating that "once farmers saw the benefits, they came back on their own."

This case demonstrates how a rural input entrepreneur can catalyze market-wide improvements. Through the **ADAPT and EXPAND** stages of systemic change, Robin's business has shifted farmer behavior, enhanced feed security, and supported a more resilient supply chain for safe meat and dairy production. His experience confirms that strengthening upstream markets is essential to sustaining productivity gains at the producer level.